

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Project acronym:	e-Skills Match
Project full title:	Open Knowledge Technologies: Mapping and validating knowledge e-Skills Match
Grant agreement no.:	ECOKT2014-7 (30-CE-0726730/00-60)
Responsible:	Panteleimon Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)
Contributors:	WP6 Partners
Document Reference:	D6.1c
Dissemination Level:	PU
Version:	Final
Date:	22/09/17
Disclaimer: This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.	

History

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
0.1	04/09/17	Initial draft	Panteleimon Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)
0.2	20/09/17	Final draft	Panteleimon Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)
0.3	22/09/17	Quality check	Myrsini Glinos (eGovlab)
1.0	22/09/17	Final reviewed deliverable	Panteleimon Kanellopoulos (Gov2u)

Peer Review

Referred version of the document	Date	Reviewer	Synthesis of comments (add your full comments in the text with note mode)
0.3	22/09/2017	Myrsini Glinos (eGovlab)	<p>Corrections in chapter 4.1.1 i.e. further explanation about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -informational website and platform website that would not confuse the reader, - reasons why added easy-to read content at the website
0.3	22/09/2017	Myrsini Glinos (eGovlab)	Correction in the information at table 14.
0.3	22/09/2017	Myrsini Glinos (eGovlab)	Further elaboration in conclusions chapter concerning lessons learnt, critical reflections about social media results and the success of the strategy that was followed in social media.

Table of contents

History	2
Peer Review	3
Table of contents	4
List of figures	6
List of tables	8
List of abbreviations	9
Executive summary	10
1 Introduction	11
1.1 The project: e-Skills Match	11
1.2 WP6 Communication and Dissemination.....	11
2 D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities: The deliverable ..	13
2.1 Scope of the deliverable	13
2.2 Intended audience of the deliverable	13
2.3 Structure of the document.....	13
2.4 Methodology	14
2.5 Quality of the document	14
2.6 Relation of the deliverable to other WP6 deliverables	14
3 Dissemination and Communication objectives for Y2	15
4 Dissemination and Communication tools and activities of Y2	16
4.1 Dissemination and Communication tools	16
4.1.1 Informational website	16
4.1.2 Social media.....	17
4.1.2.1 Facebook page.....	17
4.1.2.2 Twitter profile.....	18
4.1.2.3 LinkedIn profile.....	20
4.1.3 Newsletter Issue No.2	22
4.1.4 Press releases	22
4.1.5 Promotional materials	23
4.1.5.1 Brochure Y2	23
4.1.5.2 Factsheet Y2	24
4.1.5.3 Flyer Y2	24
4.1.5.4 Poster Y2.....	24
4.1.6 Digital publishing platforms.....	25
4.1.6.1 LinkedIn SlideShare account.....	25

4.1.6.2	Issuu profile	29
4.1.6.3	SCRIBD profile.....	31
4.1.7	Handbook	33
4.1.8	YouTube videos	34
4.1.9	PlayBuzz.....	35
4.1.10	Photo sharing websites	36
4.1.10.1	Pinterest	36
4.1.10.2	Instagram.....	38
4.2	Dissemination and Communication activities	40
4.2.1	Publications	40
4.2.1.1	Scientific article in Computer Standards & Interfaces.....	40
4.2.1.2	Book chapter in IJHCITP (<i>submitted</i>).....	40
4.2.2	Direct contact with stakeholders (<i>face to face meetings</i>).....	40
4.2.3	Communication with stakeholders.....	42
4.2.4	Organization of outreach activities	43
4.2.5	Participation in third party events.....	47
4.2.6	Media coverage	47
4.2.7	Liaison with other projects, networks & initiatives.....	48
4.2.7.1	Collaboration with other EU funded projects	48
4.2.7.2	Joinup	50
4.2.7.3	Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition group (<i>LinkedIn group</i>).....	51
4.3	Overview of dissemination tools and activities.....	52
5	Conclusions	54
	APPENDIX I – Google Analytics of project’s informational website.....	55
	APPENDIX II – Facebook Data Insights	56
	APPENDIX III – Twitter Profile Overview	57
	APPENDIX IV – SCRIBD Analytics.....	60
	APPENDIX V – Issuu Analytics	61
	APPENDIX VI – SlideShare Analytics.....	62
	APPENDIX VII – Pinterest Statistics	65
	APPENDIX VIII – 2nd Newsletter Issue	66
	APPENDIX IX – Promotional materials in EL, ES, IT.....	68
	APPENDIX X – Communication with stakeholders	70
	APPENDIX XI – Participation in third party events	82
	APPENDIX XII – Media Coverage	86

List of figures

Figure 1 : Phases of the dissemination process for Y2	15
Figure 2 : e-Skills Match Facebook Page.....	18
Figure 3 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile.....	19
Figure 4 : Follower Growth (Twitter profile)	20
Figure 5 : e-Skills Match LinkedIn Profile	21
Figure 6 : Connections Growth (LinkedIn profile)	22
Figure 7 : e-Skills Match brochure Y2 (EN)	23
Figure 8 : e-Skills Match factsheet Y2 (EN).....	24
Figure 9 : e-Skills Match flyer Y2 (EN).....	24
Figure 10 : e-Skills Match flyer Y2 (EN).....	25
Figure 11 : e-Skills Match Slideshare account	26
Figure 12 : Earned views at SlideShare (M13-M24).....	26
Figure 13 : SlideShare Top content (M13-M24).....	27
Figure 14 : Geography of the earned views (SlideShare)	27
Figure 15 : Top 10 countries (SlideShare).....	28
Figure 16 : Traffic sources (SlideShare).....	28
Figure 17 : e-Skills Match Issuu profile	30
Figure 18 : e-Skills Match Issuu profile overall performance.....	30
Figure 19 : e-Skills Match SCRIBD profile	33
Figure 20 : The Handbook (front & back page)	33
Figure 21 : e-Skills Match YouTube channel.....	35
Figure 22 : YouTube icon at e-Skills Match informational website.....	35
Figure 23 : Analytics of the e-Skills Match video on Playbuzz	36
Figure 24 : e-Skills Match Pinterest profile	37
Figure 25 : Pinterest icon at e-Skills Match informational website	37
Figure 26 : e-Skills Match Instagram profile	39
Figure 27 : Instagram icon at e-Skills Match informational website	39
Figure 28 : e-Skills Match featured on Joinup	50
Figure 29 : e-Skills Match featured on Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition (LinkedIn Group).....	51
Figure 30 : Audience overview Y2 (informational website).....	55
Figure 31 : Post reach (Facebook page).....	56
Figure 32 : Reactions (Facebook page)	56
Figure 33 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile Summary.....	57
Figure 34 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile – Most Popular Links	57
Figure 35 : Impressions for the period 01/09/16 – 30/11/16 (Twitter).....	58
Figure 36 : Impressions for the period 01/12/16 – 28/02/17 (Twitter).....	58
Figure 37 : Impressions for the period 01/03/17 – 30/06/17 (Twitter).....	58
Figure 38 : Impressions for the period 31/06/17 – 29/08/17 (Twitter).....	59
Figure 39 : Impressions for the period 30th & 31st of August 2017 (Twitter).....	59
Figure 40 : SCRIBD Analytics (Screenshot)	60
Figure 41 : Issuu Analytics (Screenshot).....	61
Figure 42 : SlideShare Analytics page 1 (Screenshot)	62
Figure 43 : SlideShare Analytics page 1 continue (Screenshot)	62
Figure 44 : SlideShare Analytics page 2 (Screenshot)	63
Figure 45 : SlideShare Analytics page 2 continue (Screenshot)	63
Figure 46 : SlideShare Analytics page 3 (Screenshot)	64
Figure 47 : Pins' impressions (Pinterest)	65

Figure 48 : Editorial (Second newsletter issue).....66
Figure 49 : e-Skills Match YouTube videos (Second newsletter issue).....66
Figure 50 : Quotes form partners (Second newsletter issue).....67
Figure 51 : Sample of the promotional material Y2 in Italian68
Figure 52 : Sample of the promotional material Y2 in Greek68
Figure 53 : Sample of the promotional materials Y2 in Spanish69

List of tables

Table 1 : Intended audience.....	13
Table 2 : Website metrics of Y2 by Google Analytics	17
Table 3 : e-Skills Match Facebook Page (status)	18
Table 4 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile (status)	19
Table 5 : Total impressions of the e-Skills Match Twitter profile.....	20
Table 6 : e-Skills Match LinkedIn Profile (status).....	22
Table 7 : List of items published on e-Skills Match Slideshare account & No. of views	29
Table 8 : List of items published on e-Skills Match Issuu profile & statistics	31
Table 9 : List of publications on e-Skills Match SCRIBD profile & No. of views	32
Table 10 : List of e-Skills Match YouTube videos & earned views.....	34
Table 11 : List of pins & No. of appearances (Pinterest)	38
Table 12 : e-Skills Match Instagram profile performance	38
Table 13 : List of uploaded photos on Instagram	40
Table 14 : Direct contact with stakeholders (face to face meetings)	42
Table 15 : Organization of outreach activities Y2.....	47
Table 16 : Media Coverage analysis	48
Table 17 : Collaboration with other EU funded projects	49
Table 18 : Other collaborative activities	50
Table 19 : Overview of dissemination tools and activities	53
Table 20 : Communication with stakeholders	81
Table 21 : Participation in third party events.....	85
Table 22 : Media coverage	106

List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
Adfor	Adfor S.p.A
DoW	Description of Work
D6.1b	D61.b First report of communication and dissemination & updated communication and dissemination plan
D6.1c	D61.c Final report of communication and dissemination activities
D6.4	D6.4 e-Skills Match Handbook
EASQ	European Area of Skills and Qualifications
EC DG CONNECT	European Commission Communications Networks, Content and Technology Directorate General
EC	European Commission
e-CF	European e-Competence Framework
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
EU	European Union
FPM	Fondazione Politecnico di Milano
Gov2u	Government To You
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
M1	Month 1
MOOCS	Massive Open Online Courses
OER	Open Education Resources
SU	Stockholm University
UAH	Universidad de Alcalá
WP	Work Package
Y1	First year
Y2	Second year

Executive summary

This document under the title D6.1c “Final Report of Communication and dissemination activities” constitutes a public deliverable of the WP6 “Communication and Dissemination” of the EC funded project, e-Skills Match.

The purpose of the current deliverable is to present a yearly report (*September 2016 – August 2017*) concerning the communication and dissemination activities that have been performed by the consortium within the second year of project’s implementation. Moreover, it provides an update on the communication tools used during the aforementioned period. It forms an update of the D6.1b “First report of communication and dissemination activities & updated communication and dissemination plan” that was submitted in September 2016 (*M13*).

D6.1c is divided into 5 chapters for ensuring that the reader acquires all the necessary information around the project without prior reading the DoW and/ or other deliverables of this work package. In no case, however, it does not substitute either the DoW or WP6 deliverables.

1 Introduction

1.1 The project: e-Skills Match

e-Skills Match “Open Knowledge Technologies: Mapping and validating knowledge” is a 24-month co-funded project by the European Commission Communications Networks, Content and Technology Directorate General (DG CONNECT), Unit for Inclusion, Skills and Youth. The project involves five consortium partners, namely Stockholm University (SU), Fondazione Politecnico di Milano (FPM), Universidad de Alcalá (UAH), Adfor S.p.A (Adfor) and Government To You (Gov2u).

The project aims to develop and demonstrate a European-wide learning technology system, dynamically adapted to changes occurring in job labor market classifications that will support (re)-training for acquiring the necessary e-Skills and digital competences to access the desirable jobs within ICT sector.

In a nutshell, the project will design, develop and test the e-Skills Match platform, which will be an e-Portfolio solution that will be hosted in a cloud environment. The system will allow individuals to create and manage their e-Portfolio, perform an e-Skills audit in order to analyse their e-Skills and digital competences, to self-assess their position in the labour environment and to plan learning pathways for complementing occupational e-skills, or in some cases to prepare for the validation of the learning outcomes by the course providers, whose courses will be included in the platform.

The tool will be consisted of the following services:

- e-competences self-assessment with the related outcomes formalized by graphs;
- e-competence / job profile training offer, including OER (Open Education Resources) and MOOCS (Massive Open On-line Courses);
- e-competence certifications offered by course providers.

All the services offered by the e-Skills Match platform will be integrated in order to assist the end users to relate the outcomes of their self-assessment to the training paths suggested by the project’s platform. The end users will be able to gain certifications after they have completed their training provided by the certified course providers.

The project’s system prototype will be tested and validated at EU level, specifically on four EU countries (Greece, Italy, Spain and Sweden).

1.2 WP6 Communication and Dissemination

WP6 is a subset of e-Skills Match project. According to the project’s DoW, WP6 aims to create awareness and understanding of the benefits of the initiative and to ensure the proper dissemination of project results towards the scientific community, business and policy stakeholders.

As the DoW clearly states “The WP will emphasize on the clustering with the ongoing projects and an attempt to influence the standards concerning areas of interest of the project as well as to raise awareness on EU instruments [European Qualifications Framework (EQF), Europass, European e-Competence Framework (e-CF), European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) etc.]. The Users Engagement Strategy developed by WP6 will target the involvement of people from the pilot sites in the learning and skills acquisition activities”.

In detail, the current WP will proceed with the implementation of the following tasks during the 24 months of the project’s duration:

- **Task 6.1** *“Planning, Coordinating and Reporting of Communication and Dissemination activities” (M01-M24)*
- **Task 6.2** *“Implementation of traditional and Web 2.0 communication activities” (M01-M24)*
- **Task 6.3** *“Develop the User Engagement Strategy “(M14-M16)*
- **Task 6.4** *“Dissemination of the project results” (M20-M24)*

2 D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities: The deliverable

2.1 Scope of the deliverable

D6.1 “Final Report of Communication and Dissemination Activities” is the eighth submitted deliverable of the WP6. The scope of this document is to present a yearly report related to the communication and dissemination activities that have been undertaken by the e-Skills Match consortium during the second year of the project. Moreover, it provides an update on the communication tools that have been used under the aforementioned period.

2.2 Intended audience of the deliverable

The intended audience of this deliverable is presented at the table below:

Intended Audience	Reasons for interest in reading
e-Skills Match consortium partners	To be informed about the WP6 communication and dissemination activities performed from M31 to M24
European Commission	This is a deliverable of e-Skills Match project and shows the progress made regarding dissemination and communication of the project
Target Groups (general public, potential users of the e-Skills Match platform, ICT practitioners, academia, training/certification institutions, etc.)	To be informed on communication and dissemination activities performed within M13-M24, get informed about the dissemination tools available online-offline, how they can get involved and test the innovative e-Skills Match platform
Representatives of entities involved in similar projects	To share knowledge, information and best practices that can be adopted and utilized in other similar projects, as well as to enhance their visibility via cross-dissemination of activities and events

Table 1 : Intended audience

2.3 Structure of the document

At the beginning of this document the reader is introduced to the project and the tasks of the work package 6. The second section describes this deliverable’s scope, its intended audience and the methodology followed for its production. The third section shortly describes the dissemination phases of Y2 and the objectives of WP6 within the same period.

The core information that constitutes the report of the performed dissemination and communication activities from September 2016 to August 2017 is included in section four. Moreover, the dissemination and communication tools used during the aforementioned period are described in the same section.

Lastly, the fifth section is the conclusion of this document.

2.4 Methodology

The current deliverable has been created by Gov2u, the responsible partner for writing and delivering this report as described in the DoW.

Each organization of the e-Skills Match consortium initially provided to WP6 leader a detailed report that concerns its performed dissemination and communication activities for Y2 (*M13-M24*). Following, these reports were analyzed and elaborated by Gov2u. The final draft of this document was delivered to the consortium for peer reviewing. All suggested corrections and comments provided by the project partners have been evaluated and incorporated by Gov2u staff to its final version.

The final version was delivered by Gov2u to the project coordinator (*SU*) in order to submit it to EC for final approval.

2.5 Quality of the document

The quality of the deliverable has been reviewed by the project coordinator and it conforms to the following criteria: e-Skills Match deliverable template, correct language and spelling, consistency with the DoW, while its content fits the purpose of the deliverable.

2.6 Relation of the deliverable to other WP6 deliverables

This deliverable is related to the following WP6 deliverables that have been submitted to EC throughout project's lifetime:

- D6.1b "First report of communication and dissemination activities & Updated Communication and Dissemination Plan" (*M13*);
- D6.3 "User Engagement Strategy" (*M16*);
- D6.2c "Second promotional materials" (*M18*);
- D6.4 "e-Skills Match Handbook" (*M23*).

3 Dissemination and Communication objectives for Y2

In e-Skills Match project's lifetime WP6 aimed to create awareness and understanding of the benefits of the initiative and to ensure the proper dissemination of project results towards the scientific community, business and policy stakeholders. The actions that should be performed in project's duration were presented in D6.1a "Communication and Dissemination Plan" and divided into three phases. So for Y2, two phases were foreseen:

- **Development Phase (M11-M17):** WP6 focused on further dissemination of the project objectives regarding the platform's wider visibility and promotion as well as users' engagement by encouraging their registration and participation in the platform. WP6 will develop a User Engagement Strategy for the above reason. Participation of partners in third party events will raise more visibility. Moreover, an updated version of promotional materials (press release, brochure, etc.) will be created focusing on the platform's launch. Also, WP6 continued expanding the network with the target groups and established new contacts.
- **Demonstration and Evaluation Phase (M18-M24):** During the final phase WP6 efforts were put on the effective promotion of the platform via online and offline activities and dissemination of the final results building on the project's favorable reputation and established relationships with the target groups during its implementation. Usability focus groups and training sessions were conducted as demonstration and evaluation activities in each country with end-users. These activities promoted the wider dissemination of the platform locally. All findings of the project were disseminated to media outlets at national and European level and via our online tools to promote the project and its platform as well as to gain acceptance for future take-up.

According to the phases mentioned above the objectives of WP6 for Y2 were:

- to ensure the platform's wider visibility and promotion
- to encourage users' engagement, registration and participation in the platform.
- plan, coordinate and report communication and dissemination activities
- effective promotion of the platform via online and offline activities
- update of the promotional materials
- develop a User Engagement Strategy
- expand the network with the target groups and establish new contacts
- to provide a Handbook illustrating functionalities and objectives of the platform.

A brief presentation of the Y2 dissemination and communication objectives can be found at **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 : Phases of the dissemination process for Y2

4 Dissemination and Communication tools and activities of Y2

This chapter constitutes the main part of the current document and gives an overview about the performed communication and dissemination activities in Y2. Additionally, it presents the dissemination tools used within the same period. Dissemination tools are the communication channels where messages from the project are conveyed to stakeholders and to the general public.

4.1 Dissemination and Communication tools

The current subchapter describes the dissemination and communication tools that the e-Skills Match used for conveying the project's main messages to stakeholders and the general public.

4.1.1 Informational website

Being the most informational and resourceful dissemination tool for users and visitors, the project website was created and launched in M3. The translated versions in Greek, Spanish, Italian and Swedish were launched in M5.

Under the framework of attracting more stakeholders and raise the traffic of the website from the desired target groups (*i.e. IT professionals, young people, unemployed and immigrants*) amendments on the website were performed in Y2. The realization of the project's platform and suggestions of the EC reviewers played also a significant role towards these changes.

In M22, the [informational website](#) was merged with the [platform's website](#)¹ by using a banner as well as a "Join" button in the menu bar so the visitor can be redirected to the log in form of the platform. Moreover, the layout of the informational website was redesigned aesthetically in sync with the platform's website. The project's platform is the "product" of our consortium so the aim of this action was to assist us in promoting the e-Skills Match as entity and at the same time to avoid any confusion by the users.

In addition, simple and informal content that best describes e-Skills Match was added in the website. Our project is addressed to certain target groups however we should not exclude anyone who is interested about it. For this reason, the content of the website was re-written with easy-to-read language without omitting any important information of the e-Skills Match. By this practice, we ensured that all website visitors would comprehend the mentioned terms and be familiarized with them. All project partners equally contributed in translating in their languages the content of the new informational website.

Regarding the performed activities in this communication tool during Y2, we continued to regularly update it mostly with project news. The dissemination materials of Y2 (*Media section*), the press releases in Y2 (*Resources section*), the second newsletter issue (*Newsletters section*), established collaborations with similar EU funded projects (*Similar projects section*) and the YouTube videos (*Media section*) were uploaded. Also, the [AddThis](#)² button and the SSL feature for secure navigation ([Cloudflare](#)) have been added. Lastly, all public deliverables will be uploaded at "Deliverables" section after their approval by the European Commission.

¹ For testing purposes it was kept as a separate website during its initial operating months

² Having the AddThis button on a website allows users to bookmark and share the content of the website.

The performance of the [e-Skills Match website](#) was measured by the Google Analytics tool for the period 1st September 2016 (M13) – 31st August 2017 (M24) and the results can be found in **Table 2**. The graphics of Google Analytics are available in **Appendix I**.

<i>Website metrics of Y2</i>	
Users (unique visitors)	1,926
Number of pageviews	14,894
Number of sessions	3,799
Percentage of New Visits	1,894 (49.9%)
Percentage of Returning Visits	1,905 (50.1%)

Table 2 : Website metrics of Y2 by Google Analytics

4.1.2 Social media

Nowadays the social media networks play a significant role in spreading information and news in a very quick and “targeted” way. The power of these networks is similar (*and sometimes stronger*) with the traditional media such as newspapers, TV and radio.

4.1.2.1 Facebook page

Facebook is an online social media and social networking service. After registering to use the site, users can create a user profile indicating their name, occupation, schools attended and so on. Users can add other users as “friends”, exchange messages, post status updates and digital photos, share digital videos and links, use various software applications (“apps”), and receive notifications when others update their profiles or make posts.³

The Facebook page of e-Skills Match was created in November 2015 and since then it has been regularly updated with project news and news related to project’s topic.

³ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook> (Wikipedia)

Figure 2 : e-Skills Match Facebook Page

During Y2, we focused on posting project news without of course excluding any interesting reads that are related with the topic of the project. Also in few posts we used paid ads for boosting them and attract more audience. The following table shows the status of the page.

<i>e-Skills Match Facebook Page</i>	
Created	November 2015 (M3)
URL	https://www.facebook.com/eskillsmatch/
Y1 measurement	94 likes
Final (Y2) measurement	194 likes
Comment: 106.38% ⁴ increase of likes was observed at the final measurement (Y2) in comparison with the Y1 measurement.	

Table 3 : e-Skills Match Facebook Page (status)

More detailed data retrieved from Facebook Insights service can be found in **Appendix II**.

4.1.2.2 Twitter profile

Twitter is an online news and social networking service where users post and interact with messages, "tweets", restricted to 140 characters. Registered users can post tweets, but those who are unregistered can only read them.⁵

The Twitter profile of the e-Skills Match was created in November 2015 and since then it has been regularly updated with project news and news related to project's topic. The deliverable D6.1b presented the performance of this profile for the first year of project's implementation.

⁴ Percentage calculation: $194 - 94 / 94 \times 100 = 106.38\%$

⁵ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Twitter> (Wikipedia)

In the current document D6.1c a detail report is presented for Y2 with data retrieved from the free versions of Twitter analytics and Hootsuite tool⁶.

Figure 3 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile

During the second year of project’s implementation we adopted a different approach in attracting followers (*especially youth*) at the e-Skills Match profile. Twitter profiles such as youth organizations, student’s organizations, Erasmus Student Networks, Europe Direct local offices etc. were followed and contacted via inbox messages for informing them about the project.

e-Skills Match Twitter Profile	
Created	November 2015 (M3)
URL	https://twitter.com/eSkillsMatch
Y1 measurement	47 followers
Final (Y2) measurement	196 followers
Comment: 317.02% ⁷ increase of followers was observed at the final measurement (Y2) in comparison with the Y1 measurement.	

Table 4 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile (status)

Figure 4 depicts the measurement (*Hootsuite tool*) of follower’s growth from 1st September 2016 until the end of project’s lifetime.

⁶ Hootsuite is a Social Media Management System that helps its users to keep track and manage their social network channels. Multiple networks such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Google+ can be managed at the same time. Moreover it provides Analytic tools for users’ profiles

⁷ Percentage calculation: $196 - 47 / 47 \times 100 = 317.02\%$

Follower Growth

Figure 4 : Follower Growth (Twitter profile)

Table 5 shows all impressions earned from 1st September 2016 until 31st August 2017. The reporting period has been divided into 5 shorter periods due to the fact that the Twitter analytics tool provides reports for 91day periods (*maximum*). The sum of all periods reflects the total earned impressions of the e-Skills Match Twitter profile for Y2.

Period	Impressions ⁸
1 st September 2016 – 30 th November 2016	Your Tweets earned 7.3K impressions over this 91 day period
1 st December 2016 – 28 th February 2017	Your Tweets earned 4.8K impressions over this 90 day period
1 st March 2017 – 30 th May 2017	Your Tweets earned 5.6K impressions over this 91 day period
31 st May 2017 – 29 th August 2017	Your Tweets earned 6.4K impressions over this 91 day period
30 th & 31 st of August 2017	Your Tweets earned 146 impressions over this 2 day period
Total impression of the profile in Y2	24,246 total impressions

Table 5 : Total impressions of the e-Skills Match Twitter profile

In **Appendix III** screenshots from Twitter analytics provide metrics for each period mentioned in **table 5**.

4.1.2.3 LinkedIn profile

LinkedIn is a business-and employment-oriented social networking service that operates via websites and mobile apps. It is mainly used for professional networking, including employers posting jobs and job seekers posting their CVs. LinkedIn allows members (*both workers and employers*) to create profiles and "connections" to each other in an online social network which

⁸ Impressions: Number of times users saw the Tweet on Twitter

may represent real-world professional relationships. Members can invite anyone (*whether an existing member or not*) to become a connection. The "gated-access approach" (*where contact with any professional requires either an existing relationship or an introduction through a contact of theirs*) is intended to build trust among the service's members.⁹

The LinkedIn profile of e-Skills Match was created in November 2015 and since then it has been regularly updated with project news and news related to project's topic. In this chapter the reader can find the progress that was made in Y2 and it concerns the communication activities performed via this social media profile.

Figure 5 : e-Skills Match LinkedIn Profile

During the second year of project's implementation we tested and used many online tools¹⁰ (*beyond project's website*) in order to convey the e-Skills Match "message" to stakeholders and general public across Europe. After the first year of the project's implementation and as the e-Skills Match platform was focusing on IT professionals, the Dissemination and Communication team concentrated on the LinkedIn profile as the most appropriate social network to communicate with this target group and respectively students.

The results of this attempt reveal its success. The e-Skills Match LinkedIn profile was embraced in pan-European level and especially in Greece where the **highest rate**¹¹ in youth unemployment and brain drain across EU member states is observed.

The following table gives an overview of the profile and the progress that was made during Y2.

<i>e-Skills Match LinkedIn Profile</i>	
Created	November 2015 (M3)
URL	https://www.linkedin.com/in/eskillsmatch
Y1 measurement	86 connections

⁹ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LinkedIn> (Wikipedia)

¹⁰ All online tools that the e-Skills Match consortium used for disseminating the project are presented in this report.

¹¹ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Unemployment_statistics

Final (Y2) measurement	1,423 connections
Comment: 1,554.65% ¹² increase of connections was observed at the final measurement (Y2) in comparison with the Y1 measurement.	

Table 6 : e-Skills Match LinkedIn Profile (status)

Figure 6 : Connections Growth (LinkedIn profile)

4.1.3 Newsletter Issue No.2

In this issue, we followed a different approach (*design and easy-to-read content*) compared with the first newsletter issue. The second issue is consisted by three sections: The first section (*editorial*) announces the availability of the e-Skills Match platform and invites the reader to test and evaluate it. The second section presents the project’s videos on YouTube and the third quotes from partners on how the e-Skills Match platform will help its users.

It has been sent by email to all subscribers as well as to target groups and similar initiatives that have been incorporated in the mailing list by the dissemination and communication team. Additionally, it is available online at e-Skills Match informational website on section [Newsletters](#).

The “subscription box” for the project newsletter appears in the “Newsletter” section but also on the homepage for easy access to the visitors and users. **Appendix VIII** presents the sections of the 2nd Newsletter Issue.

4.1.4 Press releases

The press release constitutes one of the most popular tools for communicating project’s major developments and news. Since it is distributed in a large number of recipients (*media outlets,*

¹² Percentage calculation: $1,423 - 86 / 86 \times 100 = 1,554.65\%$

similar initiatives and projects, academia, communities and networks, etc.) helps in promoting the project at national and pan-European level.

Press releases were produced throughout the project on the purpose of media engagement in the dissemination of the project's achievements and milestones. All distributed press releases are available online and can be found at the section [Resources](#).

4.1.5 Promotional materials

Marketing collaterals (*i.e. brochure, poster, factsheet, and flyer*) are a collection of dissemination and promotional tools used to support the project's identity widely, to raise awareness and visibility of the project, to attract and motivate stakeholders to get engaged to the project and its platform, as well as to be distributed to audiences during the project's presentation in events, workshops and conferences.

All promotional materials were updated for the second year of project's implementation. A new approach was adopted in design and content (easy-to-read¹³) in comparison with the promotional material of the Y1. By this practice we tried to make them more appealing to youth audience and ensure that language would not be a barrier for understanding the objectives of the project and the benefits of using the e-Skills Match platform. All materials display the EC logo and the disclaimer excluding the EC responsibility. They are available online at the project's website on section [Media](#).

4.1.5.1 Brochure Y2

The project brochure is a single sheet, A4 folding to two A5 sides (29.7cm x 21cm). The [English version](#) was primarily created and served as a tool in communicating the platform's services and attract end users in pan-European level. Later on, it was translated in partners' languages (*Greek, Swedish, Spanish and Italian*) for achieving effective promotion in pilot countries. Sample of the translated versions in partners' languages can be found at **Appendix IX**.

Figure 7 : e-Skills Match brochure Y2 (EN)

¹³ Easy-to-read means that everybody can read and understand something

4.1.5.2 Factsheet Y2

The e-Skills Match factsheet is a single sheet printed in A4 dimensions (29.7x21cm). It describes at glance the project and its objectives, the expected results and the platform’s offer to its end user. The [English version](#) is presented in **Figure 8** while sample of the translated versions in partners’ languages can be found at **Appendix IX**.

Figure 8 : e-Skills Match factsheet Y2 (EN)

4.1.5.3 Flyer Y2

The project flyer is a single sheet trifold printed in dimensions 35,8x12cm. **Figure 9** shows the **external side** of the [English version](#) which contains the following information: project logo, project name, e-Skills Match website URL, EC logo, funding details and disclaimer. The **internal side** of the flyer contains: QR code leading to the website and a catchphrase.

Figure 9 : e-Skills Match flyer Y2 (EN)

It promotes the project’s platform with short content and a catchphrase in the internal side. Sample of the translated versions in partners’ languages can be found at **Appendix IX**.

4.1.5.4 Poster Y2

The e-Skills Match poster is a single sheet printed in A3 dimensions (29.7x42cm). It contains the following information: project logo, project “motto”, QR code leading to website, EC logo,

funding details, and disclaimer. The figure below depicts the [English version](#) of the poster while a sample of the translated versions in partners' languages can be found at **Appendix IX**.

Figure 10 : e-Skills Match flyer Y2 (EN)

4.1.6 Digital publishing platforms

Electronic publishing¹⁴ (also referred to as e-publishing or digital publishing or online publishing) includes the digital publication of e-books, digital magazines, and the development of digital libraries and catalogues.

In e-Skills Match we have used three different platforms for digital publishing serving as communication tools of the project.

4.1.6.1 LinkedIn SlideShare account

LinkedIn SlideShare is a Web 2.0–based slide hosting service where users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Slide decks can then be viewed on the site itself, on hand held devices or embedded on other sites. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. It also provides to the users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content.¹⁵

The account of e-Skills Match on Slideshare was created in October 2016 (M14) and can be found at: <https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch>

¹⁴ Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_publishing (Wikipedia)

¹⁵ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SlideShare> (Wikipedia)

Figure 11 : e-Skills Match SlideShare account

The LinkedIn SlideShare provides to its users free analytics in order to measure the account’s performance. In this report we provide a summary of the e-Skills Match with screenshots. The presented data is referred to the period September 2016 (M13) - August 2017 (M24).

Figure 12 depicts the views that the published items earned during the aforementioned period.

Figure 12 : Earned views at SlideShare (M13-M24)

Figure 13 shows the published items that earned the most views (*Top 10*) for the M13 – M24 period.

Top content	
Name	Views
e-Skills Match Project Overall Presentation - year 1	139
e-Skills Match Project Poster	109
e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Swedish version	50
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Swedish version)	39
e-Skills Match Project Brochure Y2 (english version)	37
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Swedish version)	35
e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	32
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	31
e-Skills Match Project Brochure	31
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet Y2 (English Version)	30

[Top 5](#)
[Top 10](#)
[Top 20](#)

Figure 13 : SlideShare Top content (M13-M24)

Figure 14 is a world map that depicts the geography of the earned views.

Figure 14 : Geography of the earned views (SlideShare)

Figure 15 is a Top 10 list with countries that mostly viewed the e-Skills Match published items on SlideShare.

Top countries	
Name	Views
United States	320
Greece	215
Russian Federation	50
France	14
Canada	13
China	12
Italy	11
Germany	9
Ireland	8
United Kingdom	8

Figure 15 : Top 10 countries (SlideShare)

Figure 16 : Traffic sources (SlideShare)

Table 7 lists the published items on SlideShare and presents their performance (no. of views).

S/N	Item's title	No. of views
1	e-Skills Match Project Brochure Y2 (English version) - updated	41 views
2	e-Skills Match Project Flyer Y2 (English Version)	12 views
3	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Swedish version)	35 views
4	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	31 views
5	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Greek version)	13 views
6	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Italian version)	18 views

7	e-Skills Match Project Brochure	30 views
8	e-Skills Match Project Overall Presentation - year 1	141 views
9	e-Skills Match Project Poster Y2 (English Version)	22 views
10	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet Y2 (English Version)	30 views
11	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Swedish version	52 views
12	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Swedish version)	29 views
13	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Swedish version)	39 views
14	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	33 views
15	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Spanish version)	20 views
16	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Spanish version)	26 views
17	e-Skill Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Greek version	23 views
18	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Greek version)	12 views
19	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Greek version)	20 views
20	e-Skills Match Poster (shorter version) - Italian version	12 views
21	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Italian version)	9 views
22	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Italian version)	22 views
23	e-Skills Match Poster (shorter version)	11 views
24	e-Skills Match Project Poster	109 views
25	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet	20 views
26	e-Skills Match Project Brochure Y2 (English Version)	14 views

Table 7 : List of items published on e-Skills Match Slideshare account & No. of views

4.1.6.2 Issuu profile

Issuu is a free electronic publishing platform for magazines, catalogs, and newspapers.¹⁶ The e-Skills Match profile on Issuu was created in M18 and the project's promotional material of Y2 (English version) were uploaded. The public profile can be found at: <https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch>

¹⁶ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Issuu> (Wikipedia)

Figure 17 : e-Skills Match Issuu profile

The platform provides some free statistics concerning the overall performance of the profile as well as per published item.

Figure 18 : e-Skills Match Issuu profile overall performance

The explanation of the metrics terms (*as given by Issuu*) that are showcased in figure 18 is:

- **Reads:** Counted each time a user opened a publication for more than 2 seconds.
- **Impressions:** Counted each time a publication was displayed to a user in an embedded or on Issuu.
- **Followers:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Likes:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Shares:** The number of times a user shared your publication from Issuu.
- **Link-outs:** Number of clicks on a publisher made link.
- **Average time spent:** The average time readers spent reading this publication
- **Read time:** The total time readers spend reading this publication

The list with the published items on e-Skills Match profile can be found at **table 8**.

S/N	Publication's title	URL	Reads	Impressions	Average time spend	Read time
1.	e-Skills Match Project Brochure Y2 (English version)	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/e-skills_match_project_brochure_y2	6	87	0:00:23	0:02:23
2.	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet Y2 (English version)	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/factsheety2_webv	2	4	0:00:46	0:01:32
3.	e-Skills Match Project Flyer Y2 (English version)	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/flyer-eskills_for-web	2	4	0:00:16	0:00:32
4.	e-Skills Match Project Poster Y2 (English version)	https://issuu.com/home/statistics/publications/poster_for-web	3	7	0:02:53	0:08:40

Table 8 : List of items published on e-Skills Match Issuu profile & statistics

The earned impressions of each published item as originally presented by Issuu can be found at **Appendix V**.

4.1.6.3 SCRIBD profile

Scribd is a digital library, e-book and audiobook subscription service.¹⁷ The profile of e-Skills Match on SCRIBD was created in M14 and the promotional materials of Y1 and Y2 were uploaded. The public profile of the project can be found at the following link: <https://www.scribd.com/user/333902050/e-Skills-Match-Project>

All language versions of Y1 promotional materials were published as well as the English version of Y2. In total, 23 items have been uploaded at this platform. **Table 9** lists the published items on SCRIBD and presents their performance (*no. of views*) within the reporting period.

S/N	Item's title	No. of views
1	e-Skills Match Project Poster	5 views
2	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet	4 views
3	e-Skills Match Project Brochure	11 views

¹⁷ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scribd> (Wikipedia)

4	e-Skills Match Project Overall Presentation	10 views
5	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Italian version)	4 views
6	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Italian version	4 views
7	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Italian version)	5 views
8	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Italian version)	4 views
9	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Greek version)	5 views
10	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Greek version	4 views
11	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Greek version)	5 views
12	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Greek version)	8 views
13	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Swedish version)	4 views
14	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Swedish version	4 views
15	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Swedish version)	5 views
16	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Swedish version)	7 views
17	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Spanish version)	4 views
18	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	8 views
19	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	8 views
20	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Spanish version)	6 views
21	e-Skills Match Project Flyer (English version) - Year 2	14 views
22	e- Skills Match Project Factsheet (English version) - Year 2	22 views
23	e-Skills Match Project Poster (English version) - Year 2	18 views
24	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (English version) - Year 2	20 views

Table 9 : List of publications on e-Skills Match SCRIBD profile & No. of views

The original list (*screenshot*) with the earned views of each published item can be found at **Appendix IV**.

Figure 19 depicts the e-Skills Match public profile on SCRIBD.

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Figure 19 : e-Skills Match SCRIBD profile

4.1.7 Handbook

This Handbook (*user guide*) is designed to explain the functioning of each service (*tool*) that is included in the project's platform. It provides to the reader a step-by-step explanation accompanied with screenshots from the e-Skills Match platform. By using this practice we eliminate any kind of barriers that would demotivate the individuals of testing, using and exploring its full capabilities.

Figure 20 : The Handbook (front & back page)

4.1.8 YouTube videos

YouTube is a video-sharing website that allows users to upload, view, rate, share, add to favorites, report, comment on videos, and subscribe to other users. Available content includes video clips, TV show clips, music videos, short and documentary films, audio recordings, movie trailers and other content such as video blogging, short original videos, and educational videos. Unregistered users can only watch videos on the site, while registered users are permitted to upload an unlimited number of videos and add comments to videos.¹⁸

The [e-Skills Match YouTube channel](#) was created in M23 and serves as a tool for promoting the project's videos. The list with the uploaded videos is provided in **table 10**.

S/N	Video's Title	No. of Views
1.	Lorenza Leita, FPM, explains e-competence self-assessment in e-Skills Match	67 views
2.	Lorenza Leita, FPM, introducing e-CF (EN16234) and ESCO	36 views
3.	Paolo Locatelli, FPM di Milano, explains benefits of e-Skills Match in e-Health sector	38 views
4.	e-Skills Match for ICT training providers and employers	77 views
5.	e-Skills Match - The Self-Assessment	17 views
6.	e-Skills Match - The Employer	5 views
7.	e-Skills Match - The ePortfolio	6 views
8.	e-Skills Match - The Training Section	10 views
9.	e-Skills Match - The Training Institution	7 views

Table 10 : List of e-Skills Match YouTube videos & earned views

¹⁸ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/YouTube> (Wikipedia)

Figure 21 : e-Skills Match YouTube channel

Moreover, the icon of the YouTube has been added at the social media area of the project's informational website and it is linked with the e-Skills Match YouTube channel.

Figure 22 : YouTube icon at e-Skills Match informational website

4.1.9 PlayBuzz

PlayBuzz is an online publishing platform for publishers, brand agencies and individual content creators to create content in interactive formats such as polls, quizzes, lists, video snippets, slideshows, and countdowns. PlayBuzz generated content is generally associated with viral media that can be shared via social media or embedded elsewhere on the web.¹⁹ In the context of exploring and testing new tools that will help us further promote the e-Skills Match platform, we used the PlayBuzz platform.

¹⁹ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Playbuzz> (Wikipedia)

Our attempt in this platform was the creation of a “story” around of e-Skills Match using the YouTube video with the title [Lorenza Leita, FPM, explains e-competence self assessment in e-Skills Match](#). The story that we created had the title: [Map your journey to a new career](#)

In order to log in to this platform you need to use a Facebook profile. In our case we used the corporate Facebook profile of Gov2u. Unfortunately, a Facebook page (e.g. e-Skills Match page) cannot be used for the log in process.

The analytics (*performance*) of the created “stories” within this tools are provided for free. The following figure presents the performance of the e-Skills Match story.

Figure 23 : Analytics of the e-Skills Match video on Playbuzz

4.1.10 Photo sharing websites

4.1.10.1 Pinterest

Pinterest is an internet photo sharing and publishing service that allows users to "Pin" pictures they like and upload their own recommendations to their "pinboards". Users can visit other pinboards, 're-pin' images to their own pinboards, or 'like' photos.²⁰

We have created the e-Skills Match account in Pinterest and project’s profile can be found at the following link: <https://gr.pinterest.com/eskillsmatch/>

²⁰ Source: <https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pinterest> (Simple English Wikipedia)

Figure 24 : e-Skills Match Pinterest profile

Moreover, the icon of this social media account has been added at the footer of the project’s informational website so visitors can discover the project’s profile and follow it.

Figure 25 : Pinterest icon at e-Skills Match informational website

Table 12 lists the pins that we have created and presents their performance (no. of impressions).

S/N	Pin’s URL	No. of impressions
1.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884556991/	39
2.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557517/	32
3.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557527/	29
4.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557532/	35
5.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557566/	23

6.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576082/	3,309
7.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576087/	53
8.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576111/	80
9.	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576118/	2,260
Total pins impressions		5,862

Table 11 : List of pins & No. of appearances (Pinterest)

Screenshots of the statistics provided by Pinterest can be found in **Appendix VII**.

4.1.10.2 Instagram

Instagram is a mobile, desktop, and Internet-based photo-sharing application and service that allows users to share pictures and videos either publicly or privately. Instagram lets registered users upload photos or videos to the service. Users can apply various digital filters to their images, and add locations through geotags. They can add hashtags to their posts, linking the photos up to other content on Instagram featuring the same subject or overall topic. Users can connect their Instagram account to other social media profiles, enabling them to share photos to those profiles as well.²¹

The project's account was created in M18 in order to assist the communication activities of the project. Instagram is very popular in the young audience and assisted us in raising the visibility of the project also to this audience. The profile's name is **eskillsmatchproject** and can be found at: <https://www.instagram.com/eskillsmatchproject/>

The table below briefly presents the profile's performance.

e-Skills Match Instagram profile performance	
Number of posts	4
Number of Followers	37
Number of following	110

Table 12 : e-Skills Match Instagram profile performance

²¹ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Instagram> (Wikipedia)

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Figure 26 : e-Skills Match Instagram profile

The icon of Instagram has been added on the informational website at the social media area.

Figure 27 : Instagram icon at e-Skills Match informational website

The list of the uploaded items at Instagram and their metrics can be found at the table below.

Photo's topic	Url	Likes	Comments
e-Skills Match Project Meeting in Athens	https://www.instagram.com/p/BSf_I8tBWII/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject	12	0
Usability workshop in University of Alcalá	https://www.instagram.com/p/BRdB_j0Biap/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject	21	0

Usability workshop at Gov2u premises in Athens (1 st workshop)	https://www.instagram.com/p/BQz1eolBchD/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject	31	0
Usability workshop at Gov2u premises in Athens (2 nd workshop)	https://www.instagram.com/p/BQ2YZRXBNhD/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject	34	6

Table 13 : List of uploaded photos on Instagram

4.2 Dissemination and Communication activities

The current subchapter describes the dissemination and communication activities that the e-Skills Match consortium performed under the reporting period.

4.2.1 Publications

4.2.1.1 Scientific article in Computer Standards & Interfaces

Project partners Luis Fernández-Sanz (UAH), Josefa Gómez-Pérez (UAH) and Ana Castillo-Martínez (UAH) published an article titled “*e-Skills Match: A framework for mapping and integrating the main skills, knowledge and competence standards and models for ICT occupations*”. It is part of a scientific journal named “*Computer Standards & Interfaces*” ranked as Q2 in the world prestigious ranking of JCR by ISI and it’s featured in the 51st volume.

The article defines the ways in which the e-Skills Match Framework will function. Specifically, it will enable the development of future support systems which may provide self-assessment functions for job candidates, recommender modules to guide their training to target occupations and the possibility of knowledge validation options aligned to the specific set of skills, knowledge and competences used as basic elements of the model.

The free pre-print version of this article can be found at [ResearchGate](#). The final version is available at [ScienceDirect](#).

4.2.1.2 Book chapter in IJHCITP (*submitted*)

The findings of the e-Skills Match project were further disseminated by UAH with the submission of a book chapter to the **Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals (IJHCITP)**. The book chapter has the title “*Analysis of the European ICT Competence Frameworks*”²² and it has been submitted to the journal for further publication

4.2.2 Direct contact with stakeholders (*face to face meetings*)

Face to face meetings were held by the consortium throughout Y2 aiming to expand the network of interested parties and individuals towards the e-Skills Match platform. **Table 14** presents all relevant information about them.

²² Not available link at the submission day of the current document

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name and type of the contact</i>	<i>Date of the meeting</i>	<i>Venue/Location of the meeting</i>	<i>Activity description (short description of the outcome of the meeting, what we gained from it)</i>
FPM	UIL TUCS Networkers; trade union branch devoted to networkers	22 February 2017	FPM – Campus Leonardo	Usability Focus Group with selected stakeholders for testing and verifying the prototype
FPM	Engineering Associates, Small company	22 February 2017	FPM – Campus Leonardo	Usability Focus Group with selected stakeholders for testing and verifying the prototype
FPM	Polihub Servizi SRL, Start up district and business incubator	22 February 2017	FPM – Campus Leonardo	Usability Focus Group with selected stakeholders for testing and verifying the prototype
FPM	OXYS Consulting, Small organisation	22 February 2017	FPM – Campus Leonardo	Usability Focus Group with selected stakeholders for testing and verifying the prototype
FPM	Rino Canizzaro, Council member of ASSINTEL national association of ICT enterprises.	1 st June 2017	Milan – Politecnico di Milano	A smart talk on the opportunities of eSKM against the very last news emerging from the Italian Observatory on ICT led by ASSINTEL, in collaboration with

				AICA, AGID et Al, officially presented a few days later in June 6 in Rome. The outcome were soon after shared in the open event dedicated to eSKM.
FPM	Fabio Massimo, CNA - ICT (National Confederation of SMEs – area ICT and standardisation s) – Chairman CEN Project Committee 428 “Digital Competencies and ICT Professionalism ”	1 st June 2017 1 st August 2017	Milan, FPM	An internal debate on the eSKM against the ongoing activities of the CEN TC 428 “Digital Competencies and ICT Professionalism”. Some of the outcomes were proposed to the public during the open event with stakeholders. In August, an interview is planned to be published online.
eGovlab	Arbetsförmedlingen Swedish Public employment service	30 June	Stockholm at Arbetsförmedlingen’s offices	Demo of platform and discussion around future opportunities for collaboration (target group: job seekers in Sweden). Discussions are ongoing.

Table 14 : Direct contact with stakeholders (face to face meetings)

4.2.3 Communication with stakeholders

As mentioned in the DoW and D6.1a Communication and Dissemination Plan (M2), it is among the responsibilities of WP6 leader to create mailing lists and establish contacts with networks and communities that are related to the project’s thematic area. In Y2 these mailing lists were updated and enriched by Gov2u with the close collaboration of the consortium. Additionally, the consortium used a mixture of methods (*such as newsletters, press releases, social media,*

emails etc.) for communicating with the stakeholders. All the performed actions are presented in the **Appendix X**.

4.2.4 Organization of outreach activities

The following table indicates all the outreach²³ activities that e-Skills Match partners organized during Y2.

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the event</i>	<i>Date of the event</i>	<i>Location of the event (city, country)</i>	<i>Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)</i>	<i>Outcome of the activity</i>
eGovlab	eGovlab presentation to delegation from Sri Lanka and India	24 October 2016	Stockholm	eGovlab presented the key work and EU projects including eSkills Match to two delegations (<i>Sri Lanka and India</i>).	Dissemination on global level. Exchange of ideas and knowledge.
eGovlab	Usability workshop: eSkills Match platform Evaluation	21 December 2016	Stockholm	eGovlab conducted a usability workshop as part of WP7 activities. The aim of the workshop was to evaluate the platform prototype from a usability perspective. There were 8 participants who had an ICT background.	Data collection for usability evaluation from ICT professionals for the means of WP7.
UAH	Usability workshop	16 February 2017	Alcalá de Henares, Spain	Workshop performed with experts to evaluate the usability (<i>and accesibility</i>) of the e-Skills	Evaluate the usability and accessibility of the the e-Skills Match Framework

²³ Outreach activities: Meetings / workshops / events / webcasts / webinars / press conferences

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

				Match Framework	
Adfor	Usability workshop	18 February 2017	Adfor Assago	Workshop performed with experts to evaluate the usability (<i>and accesibility</i>) of the e-Skills Match Framework	Evaluate the usability and accessibility of the e-Skills Match Framework
Gov2U	e-Skills Match Platform Usability Workshop	21 February 2017	Gov2U office, Athens, Greece	Gov2U conducted a workshop to test the Usability of the e-Skills Match Platform. 3 ICT professionals attended the workshop during the first day.	The ICT professionals navigated the e-Skills Match Platform. They tested its main features (self-assessment tool, e-portfolio) and evaluated its usability and expressed their opinions on how the platform could be improved.
eGovlab	eGovlab presentation to delegation from Uganda	21 February 2017	Stockholm	eGovlab presented the key work and EU projects including eSkills Match to a delegation of Uganda.	Dissemination on global level. Exchange of ideas and knowledge.
FPM	Usability Focus Group	22 February 2017	FPM – Campus Leonardo, Milan (IT)	Testing the usability of the platform prototype with the stakeholders	Level of satisfaction on the tool; suggestions and comments for further adjustment

Gov2u	e-Skills Match Platform Usability Workshop	22 February 2017	Gov2U office Athens, Greece	Gov2U conducted a workshop to test the usability of the e-Skills Match Platform. 4 ICT professionals took part in the workshop during the second day	The ICT professionals navigated the e-Skills Match Platform. They tested its main features (<i>self-assessment tool, e-portfolio</i>) and evaluated its usability and expressed their opinions on how the platform could be improved.
eGovlab	End-User Training Session	29 May 2017	Dept. of Computer and Systems Sciences, DSV SU, Stockholm	20 participants (<i>ICT students and academics</i>) tested the platform and were trained on how to use it	Awareness, training, feedback
FPM	“Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell’ICT”	01 June 2017	Politecnico di Milano, Aula Magna – P.zza L. da Vinci 32, Milano (Italy) 9:00 – 11:00	The event has presented the project and the web platform to the public. We had 37 registered and around 40 attendees (<i>students, companies, universities, training bodies and associations</i>).	The project e-Skills Match gained a large visibility into the FPM network and in the community of Politecnico di Milano University
FPM	“Competenze digitali, mercato e	01 June 2017	Politecnico di Milano, Aula F1.1	Planned soon after the open event, it	It promoted the project with HR

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

	percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT" – Training Session		P.zza L. da Vinci 32, Milano (<i>Italy</i>) 11:20 – 13:00	proposed a session to access the platform prototype, to train participants how to use it and compare pro and cons from the stakeholders' perspective. It was participated by 14 people.	representatives, ICT professionals, ICT students, ICT small and medium enterprises.
UAH	WP5 Workshop	07 June 2017	Alcalá de Henares, Spain	Workshop performed with experts to evaluate the usability (<i>and accessibility</i>) of the e-Skills Match Framework	Evaluate the usability and accessibility of the e-Skills Match Framework
UAH	Marcos europeos de competencias profesionales TIC: Experiencias y proyectos	07 June 2017	Alcalá de Henares, Spain	Project's presentation carried out in an event entitled "Marcos europeos de competencias profesionales TIC: Experiencias y proyectos" carried out in the University of Alcalá on June 7th, 2017.	Presentation of European projects related to ICT European frameworks.
ADFOR	WP5 Workshop	07 June 2017	Adfor Assago	Workshop performed with experts to evaluate the usability (<i>and accesibility</i>) of the e-Skills	Evaluate the usability and accessibility of the e-Skills Match Framework

				Match Framework	
UAH	WP5 Workshop	14 June 2017	Alcalá de Henares, Spain	Workshop performed with experts to evaluate the usability (<i>and accessibility</i>) of the e-Skills Match Framework	Evaluate the usability and accessibility of the e-Skills Match Framework
Gov2u	e-Skills Match Training session with end users	23 June 2017	Gov2U office Athens, Greece	Gov2U conducted a workshop in order to train ICT professionals how to use the e-Skills Match Platform. Five ICT professionals physically attended the workshop, while 3 others viewed the presentation and the training session through the web (<i>skype</i>).	Promote the e-Skills match platform, train IT professionals on the platform and receive feedback

Table 15 : Organization of outreach activities Y2

4.2.5 Participation in third party events

The project partners throughout Y2 continued to promote the e-Skills Match in third party events across Europe. The project was presented in 11 events related to the project's topic. For avoiding excessive details that would demotivate the reader to continue reading this document we provide the full list of these events and their description at **Appendix XI**.

4.2.6 Media coverage

The e-Skills Match project attracted a lot of attention from various media outlets. For example the CEPIS [press release](#) and [newsletter](#), [AENU](#)²⁴, [Tecnews](#), [Pledge Viewer](#) website, Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals.

²⁴ Asociacion de Enseñantes Universitarios de la Informatica

Moreover e-Skills Match partners promoted the project using their organization's online and offline communication tools such as websites, social media profiles, newsletters (*online and printed versions*) etc. These items include press releases, articles, interviews, news items, etc.

In **Appendix XII**, all items referred to e-Skills Match are presented in detail. However, for reader's ease, we present a summary of these activities as a quantitative measurement of the e-Skills Match press coverage.

<i>Type of reference</i>	<i>No. of references</i>
Third Party - Online & Offline (reports about e-Skills Match in newspapers, magazines, websites and other media e.g. social media profiles)	<u>27</u>
e- Skills Match Partners - Online & Offline (reports about e-Skills Match in partners' websites, press releases, newsletters and other media e.g. social media profiles)	<u>43</u>
Other (YouTube, Scribd, Pinterest, Instagram, Issuu, SlideShare, PlayBuzz)	<u>77</u>
Total	<u>147</u>

Table 16 : Media Coverage analysis

4.2.7 Liaison with other projects, networks & initiatives

Effective networking is about building strong and useful relationships and liaisons over time that can lead to mutual understanding, trust, acceptance and benefits with similar EU projects and other networks and initiatives. Such liaisons and networks can help in our effort to raise the project's positive reputation and take-up of its solution in the long term.

During the reporting period, the effort to approach and collaborate with other projects and networks continued and some progress was made.

4.2.7.1 Collaboration with other EU funded projects

The first year of the project's implementation as mentioned in D6.1b we had identified and contacted 14 EU funded project's related to similar thematic areas with e-Skills Match. Under this framework we continued the efforts of Y1 in order to establish tangible collaborations with the identified projects. Most of the identified projects had either ended their lifecycle or did not respond to the communication (*via emails*) attempts for further collaboration. However, we managed to establish very important synergies with similar project that would help us also to promote the e-Skills Match outcomes beyond the end of its lifetime. The table below gives a detailed report for the performed actions with these projects.

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the project you collaborated with</i>	<i>Contact person or organization</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description of the collaboration activity</i>
Gov2u	VINA project (Erasmus+)	Ms. Despina Kanellopoulos	10/07/2017	Establishment of cross dissemination synergy

		(Project & Business Developer at e-Compass)		between VINA project and e-Skills Match. Additionally, letter of support towards e-Skills Match was provided.
Gov2u	BizMOOC project (Erasmus+)	Christian Friedl (Project Coordinator BizMOOC)	07/07/2017	Establishment of cross dissemination synergy between BIZMOOC project and e-Skills Match. Additionally, letter of support towards e-Skills Match was provided.
Gov2u	MOOQ (Erasmus +)	Dr. Christian M. Stracke (ICDE Chair in OER)	29/06/2017	Establishment of cross dissemination synergy between MOOQ project and e-Skills Match.

Table 17 : Collaboration with other EU funded projects

The established collaborations are available online at project's website on section "[Similar Projects](#)". Moreover, the e-Skills Match consortium had established other important collaborations as presented below:

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name of the project you collaborated with</i>	<i>Contact person or organization</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description of the collaboration activity</i>
FPM, ADFOR, UAH	e-CF COUNCIL, 562364 – EPP- 1-2015- IT-EPPKA – SSA	EXIN, Jan Dirx	From April 2016 on	Synergies in developing an e-Competence Qualification Profile frame that includes ESCO references and detailed information. The e-Skills Match results contribute in the methodology to follow. The framework developed in both the projects try also to keep mutual coherence in format and cross references.

<p>FPM, ADFOR, UAH</p>	<p>e-CF COUNCIL, 562364 – EPP- 1- 2015- IT-EPPKA – SSA</p>	<p>bITa, Fritz Bussemaker</p>	<p>From July 2016 on</p>	<p>Collaboration in developing Learning Units, e-CF competence-based, for training qualification programmes. E-Skills Match provides detailed information coming out from merging ESCO and eCF content that are essential to create the needed cross-references among Learning Units, e-CF competences and ICT professional roles.</p>
--------------------------------	--	-----------------------------------	------------------------------	--

Table 18 : Other collaborative activities

4.2.7.2 Joinup

[Joinup](#) is a collaborative platform created by the European Commission and funded by the European Union via the Interoperability Solutions for Public Administrations (ISA) Programme. It offers several services that aim to help e-Government professionals share their experience with each other and also hopes to support them to find, choose, re-use, develop and implement interoperability solutions. We continue using the platform to disseminate project news (press release, newsletters, marketing material, etc.) and to reach great audiences at pan-European level.

Figure 28 : e-Skills Match featured on Joinup

4.2.7.3 Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition group (*LinkedIn group*)

Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition group is a LinkedIn group created by the European Commission. The about section of this group mentions:

The European Commission calls on Member States and stakeholders, including social partners, to pledge action and to identify and share best practices, to tackle the digital skills gaps throughout Europe. Member States are asked to develop comprehensive national digital skills strategies by mid-2017 on the basis of targets set by the end of 2016. It also invites Member States to establish national digital skills coalitions, involving governments, businesses, as well as education, training and labour market stakeholders. In addition, it calls for concrete measures to bring digital skills to all levels of education and training, supporting teachers and educators and promoting active involvement of business and other organisations

The group aims at facilitating the interaction between the people and the organisations active on themes related to the Grand Coalition for Digital Jobs. Participation is open to any stakeholder with a clear and direct relation to these themes. For viewing the posts of the LinkedIn group of [Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition](#) you need to ask to join.

e-Skills Match project, member of this group, had all its posts accepted and featured. This group was an important channel for transmitting the project's developments as all its members are involved with the aforementioned themes.

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn group page for "Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition" with 1,249 members. A featured post from "e-Skills Match" is visible, titled "e-Skills Match Platform Available For Testing – Press release". The post text states: "The e-Skills Match project announces the availability of its demo platform for testing and users are invited to evaluate it. In a glance, with the e-Skills Match platform: > We help you to discover the tailored-made courses through MOOCs and OERs that ... Show more". Below the text is a promotional image for the "skills match" platform with the text "Map your Journey to a New Career" and a "GET STARTED" button. The image also includes a "PRESS RELEASE" label and a date of "Thursday, 19/07/2017". To the right of the post, there is an "ABOUT THIS GROUP" section with a description of the group's mission and a "MEMBERS" section showing 1,249 members and an "Invite others" button. At the bottom right, there is a "Find your next opportunity" section with an "Add your position" button.

Figure 29 : e-Skills Match featured on Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition (LinkedIn Group)

4.3 Overview of dissemination tools and activities

This subchapter presents in short the dissemination tools utilized from M13 to M24 and the performance of the dissemination activities within the same period. The table that follows provides this information:

<i>Type of tool</i>	<i>Type of measurement</i>	<i>Number</i>
Informational Website	Number of pageviews	14,894
	Number of sessions <i>(number of visits)</i>	3,799
	Number of users <i>(number of unique visitors)</i>	1,926
Social Media	Facebook Likes <i>(Total likes minus Y1 likes)</i>	100 <i>(194-94)</i>
	Twitter Followers <i>(Total followers minus Y1 followers)</i>	149 <i>(196-47)</i>
	Twitter profile Impressions	24,246
	LinkedIn connections <i>(Total connections minus Y1 connections)</i>	1,337 <i>(1,423-86)</i>
Digital publishing platforms	Number of items uploaded at Scribd	24
	Number of items uploaded at Issuu	4
	Number of items uploaded at SlideShare	26
Photo sharing websites	Number of posts at Instagram	4
	Number of pins at Pinterest	9
	Number of pin impressions at Pinterest	5,810
YouTube	Number of YouTube videos	9
Press release	Number of Press releases	2
Newsletter	Newsletters issues	1
Outreach activities	Number of outreach activities	16
Media coverage	Number of references in media	147

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

	(radio, TV, newspapers, magazines, informational websites, portals, platforms, partners' social media, partners' websites, blog posts)	
Third party events	Number of times participated in third party events	11
Publications	Number of publications	2 (1 published and 1 submitted)

Table 19 : Overview of dissemination tools and activities

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable we presented a yearly report about the dissemination and communication activities made by the e-Skills Match consortium under the period September 2016 – August 2017. Also the dissemination and communication tools were described and their performance within the reporting period was measured.

Nevertheless, measurements in tools' performance were conducted throughout Y2 and their results were evaluated by the dissemination and communication team. This practice led in applying corrective actions when necessary mostly in social media profiles. Also, the strategy that was followed in social media profiles was adjusted as the e-Skills Match platform focused on IT professionals.

Thus, we concentrated our efforts in *the LinkedIn profile* without of course neglecting to retain the rest of profiles. The result of this attempt reveals its success. The connections of the e-Skills Match LinkedIn profile were increased in 1,554.65% compared with the Y1 measurement. This profile served as a very important channel in conveying the e-Skills Match "messages".

Beyond the communication tools, the project's actions attracted a lot of attention from various media. Few of the most important media that our project was featured on are the CEPIS press release and newsletter, the AENUI, the Tecnonews, the Pledge Viewer website, and the Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals.

Summarizing, we used a mix of tools and activities for achieving the effective communication of the project primarily to the target groups and pilot countries and following to the general audience in pan-European level. All partners attained to promote the e-Skills Match in their countries and created the basis for exploiting its outcomes in the future.

APPENDIX I – Google Analytics of project’s informational website

The most important data related to the website can be found in **figure 30**.

Figure 30 : Audience overview Y2 (informational website)

APPENDIX II – Facebook Data Insights

For measuring the performance of the e-Skills Match Facebook Page we used the Facebook insights. Insights is a free service for all Facebook Pages and Facebook Platform application and websites. Facebook Insights provides Facebook Page owners and Facebook Platform developers with metrics around their content.

Below are the most important data retrieved from e-Skills Match Facebook page Insights for the reporting period September 2016 (M13) - August 2017 (M24).

Figure 31 : Post reach (Facebook page)

Figure 32 : Reactions (Facebook page)

APPENDIX III – Twitter Profile Overview

For measuring the performance of the e-Skills Match Twitter profile we used a combination of tools i.e. the free versions of the Hootsuite tool and Twitter Analytics. The following figures (*screenshots*) present a profile summary as retrieved from the Hootsuite tool concerning the reporting period (*September 2016 - August 2017*).

Sep 01, 2016 - Aug 31, 2017

Profile Summary

Figure 33 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile Summary

Most Popular Links

Rank	Date	Post	Clicks
1	Aug 9, 2017	http://ow.ly/39MO30eay7N https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lt7OqUou6Y&lis... e-Skills Match for #ICT #training_providers and #employers http://ow.ly/39MO30eay7N	11 clicks
2	Aug 4, 2017	http://ow.ly/ToVF30e8Qe2 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LNHcj67mpE&lis... Lorenza Leita, FPM, explains #ecompetence self assessment in e-Skills Match http://ow.ly/ToVF30e8Qe2	7 clicks
3	Aug 4, 2017	http://ow.ly/YPXX30e8Q3l https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H9PWN1ykv50&ind... Lorenza Leita, FPM, introducing e-CF (EN16234) and ESCO http://ow.ly/YPXX30e8Q3l	6 clicks
4	Aug 3, 2017	http://ow.ly/qdUw30e8PnZ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lt7OqUou6Y&lis... e-Skills Match for ICT training providers and employers http://ow.ly/qdUw30e8PnZ	4 clicks
5	Aug 17, 2017	http://ow.ly/Aret30eayCT http://www.eskillsmatch.eu/en/?platform=hootsuite The e-Skills Match project platform is available for users. Find YOUR Top Profile Matches http://ow.ly/Aret30eayCT	4 clicks
6	Aug 11, 2017	http://ow.ly/QgAl30eayps https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LNHcj67mpE&ind... Lorenza Leita explains #ecompetence #self_assessment in e-Skills Match http://ow.ly/QgAl30eayps	3 clicks
7	Aug 25, 2017	http://ow.ly/F59w30eazmC https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H9PWN1ykv50&ind... Lorenza Leita introduces the two referent #frameworks which e-Skills Match is based on: #e-CF 3.0 and #ESCO. http://ow.ly/F59w30eazmC	2 clicks
8	Aug 4, 2017	http://ow.ly/Hxnq30e8QtW https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DW7R7zyUodo&lis... Paolo Locatelli, FPM di Milano, explains benefits of e-Skills Match in #eHealth sector http://ow.ly/Hxnq30e8QtW	2 clicks
9	Aug 4, 2017	http://ow.ly/1g6E30ea6a7 http://www.eskillsmatch.eu/en/medias?platform=h... The e-Skills Match #videos are now available!! You can find them at our project's website on section #Media: http://ow.ly/1g6E30ea6a7	2 clicks

Figure 34 : e-Skills Match Twitter Profile – Most Popular Links

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Figure 35 : Impressions for the period 01/09/16 – 30/11/16 (Twitter)

Figure 36 : Impressions for the period 01/12/16 – 28/02/17 (Twitter)

Figure 37 : Impressions for the period 01/03/17 – 30/06/17 (Twitter)

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Your Tweets earned **6.4K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Figure 38 : Impressions for the period 31/06/17 – 29/08/17 (Twitter)

Your Tweets earned **146 impressions** over this **2 day** period

Figure 39 : Impressions for the period 30th & 31st of August 2017 (Twitter)

APPENDIX IV – SCRIBD Analytics

Analytics of SCRIBD are available at the following figures. They are provided as originally presented by SCRIBD. By using this practice we ensure that the reader has a transparent view of the WP6 activities and results for promoting the e-Skills Match project.

The screenshot shows the SCRIBD Analytics interface. The browser address bar displays 'Secure | https://www.scribd.com/stats'. The interface includes a search bar and navigation options like 'Upload' and 'Saved'. The main content area displays a table with two columns: 'Title' and 'Total Views'. The table lists various documents related to the e-Skills Match project, including factheets, brochures, posters, and presentations in multiple languages (English, Greek, Spanish, Swedish, Italian, Greek).

Title	Total Views
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (English version) - Year 2	23
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (English version) - Year 2	21
e-Skills Match Project Poster (English version) - Year 2	19
e-Skills Match Project Flyer (English version) - Year 2	15
e-Skills Match Project Brochure	12
e-Skills Match Project Overall Presentation	11
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Greek version)	9
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	9
e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	9
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Swedish version)	8
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Spanish version)	7
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Swedish version)	6
e-Skills Match Project Poster (Greek version)	6
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Italian version)	6
e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Greek version)	6
e-Skills Match Project Poster	6
e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Italian version	5
e-Skills Match Project Poster (Swedish version)	5
e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Swedish version	5
e-Skills Match Project Poster (Spanish version)	5
e-Skills Match Project Poster (Italian version)	5
e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Greek version	5
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet	5
e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Italian version)	5

Figure 40 : SCRIBD Analytics (Screenshot)

APPENDIX V – Issuu Analytics

Performance metrics of Issuu are available at the following figures. They are provided as originally presented by Issuu. By using this practice we ensure that the reader has a transparent view of the WP6 activities and results for promoting the e-Skills Match project.

All Publications

Click on the the title to see the detailed statistics of an individual publication

	Title	Reads	Impressions	Avg. Time Spent
	e-Skills Match Project Poste...	3	7	2:53
	e-Skills Match Project Flyer ...	2	4	0:16
	e-Skills Match Project Facts...	2	4	0:46
	e-Skills Match Project Broch...	2	35	0:45

Figure 41 : Issuu Analytics (Screenshot)

APPENDIX VI – SlideShare Analytics

Analytics of SlideShare are available at the following figures. They are provided as originally presented by Slideshare. By using this practice we ensure that the reader has a transparent view of the WP6 activities and results for promoting the e-Skills Match project

Figure 42 : SlideShare Analytics page 1 (Screenshot)

Figure 43 : SlideShare Analytics page 1 continue (Screenshot)

Figure 44 : SlideShare Analytics page 2 (Screenshot)

Figure 45 : SlideShare Analytics page 2 continue (Screenshot)

Figure 46 : SlideShare Analytics page 3 (Screenshot)

APPENDIX VII – Pinterest Statistics

Performance metrics of Pinterest are available at the following figures. They are provided as originally presented by Pinterest. By using this practice we ensure that the reader has a transparent view of the WP6 activities and results for promoting the e-Skills Match project.

Figure 47 : Pins' impressions (Pinterest)

APPENDIX VIII – 2nd Newsletter Issue

The following figures depict the sections of the second newsletter issue.

Figure 48 : Editorial (Second newsletter issue)

Figure 49 : e-Skills Match YouTube videos (Second newsletter issue)

Quotes from partners

e-Skills Match is an innovative platform prototype. It is a product of successful teamwork, united and inspired by everyone involved in the consortium. Behind every work there are individuals who make its success possible. We'd like to share with you some of the faces behind e-Skills Match and how they believe the prototype platform will help its users. Here is what they said:

Pantalis Kanellopoulos
Communications Officer at Gov2u

"I strongly believe that e-Skills Match platform will help young people to understand the ICT skills demand in the modern labour market. Let's tackle together the youth unemployment!"

Luis Fernandez
Associate professor and lead researcher at University of Alcalá

"e-Skills Match has gone a step further from what we are used to in e-skills management. Now the link to training offer and the use of real online CV based on a portfolio of evidences and merits mapped to e-skills is a reality for candidates, employers and recruiters"

Figure 50 : Quotes form partners (Second newsletter issue)

APPENDIX IX – Promotional materials in EL, ES, IT

Promotional materials samples in partners' languages can be found below.

Figure 51 : Sample of the promotional material Y2 in Italian

Figure 52 : Sample of the promotional material Y2 in Greek

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

The figure displays three promotional materials for the e-Skills Match platform in Spanish. The largest material is a graphic with a staircase design, divided into three steps:

- Top Step (Red):** **¡Empieza el viaje hacia una nueva carrera profesional!**
¿Quieres saber si tus habilidades en TIC están a la altura de tu futura carrera profesional? ¡Prueba y descubre!
Descubre los cursos hechos a medida a través de cursos online MOOC y recursos abiertos (PEA) que te proporcionan las habilidades más demandadas para tu siguiente paso en tu trayectoria profesional.
Enriquece tu e-Portfolio y llega a los empleadores que buscan profesionales de las TIC que cuenten con tus habilidades.
Includes a QR code and the text "EMPEZAR" and "www.eskillsmatch.eu".
- Middle Step (Teal):** **¿Preparado para llevar tu carrera profesional al siguiente nivel?**
Enriquece y valida tus conocimientos
Aumenta tu e-Portfolio
Promociona tus habilidades en TIC
Includes the "skills match" logo and "www.eskillsmatch.eu".
- Bottom Step (Red):** Includes the "skills match" logo and "www.eskillsmatch.eu".

Below the staircase graphic is a small text block: "El proyecto e-Skills Match está cofinanciado por la Dirección General de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica (DG CONNECT) de la Comisión Europea, Unidad de Innovación, Habilidades y Juventud, contrato de servicios (CSC) 2014-1-1-01-002-01/2014-0018." and a disclaimer: "Este material refleja únicamente la opinión del autor. La Comisión Europea no se hace responsable del uso que pueda hacerse de la información que contiene."

Two smaller posters are also shown:

- Left Poster (Red/Black):** **DESCUBRE...** Cursos online a medida para impulsar tus habilidades en TIC. **ENRIQUECE...** tu e-Portfolio. **Y LLEGA A LOS RECLUTADORES que buscan profesionales de las TIC con tus habilidades**. **DESCUBRE...** prueba y descubre si tus habilidades en las TIC están a la altura del mercado laboral. Includes the "skills match" logo, "EMPIEZA AHORA", and the same small text block as above.
- Right Poster (Red/Black):** **¡DEJA DE DAR VUELTAS! ELIGE EL CURSO CORRECTO**. **¡DESCUBRE CÓMO LA PLATAFORMA e-SKILLS MATCH PUEDE PROPORCIONARTE LA SOLUCIÓN PARA TU SIGUIENTE PASO PROFESIONAL!**. Includes a QR code, "EMPEZAR", and the same small text block as above.

Figure 53 : Sample of the promotional materials Y2 in Spanish

APPENDIX X – Communication with stakeholders

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Name and type of the contact</i>	<i>Date of communication</i>	<i>Reason of communication</i>	<i>Activity description (short description of the outcome of the communication, what we gained from it)</i>
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan page has 1554 "Like".	20/10/2016	e-Skills Match Overall Presentation available on Slideshare	Results: 60 people reached, 4 "Like", 1 "Click".
FPM	Article on FPM newsletter – online version (30,000 email contacts)	14/11/2016	Promotion of the project	e-Skills Match gained a large visibility into the FPM network
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan page has 1554 "Like".	02/12/2016	European Commission launches Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition	Results: 96 people reached, 2 "Like", 4 "Click".
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan page has 1554 "Like".	07/12/2016	Article on e-Skills Match / Newsletter FPM	Results: 540 people reached, 3 "Like", 11 "Click".
FPM	NCR Corporation	16/2/2017	Involvement in the D2.1 online survey	Opening contact for participation in the project activities linked to the platform testing, launch and promotion

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

FPM	WebScience, HRM	17/2/2017	Involvement in the D2.1 online survey	Description of the project and the survey
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan page has 1554 "Like".	24/02/2017	Photos of e-Skills Match Italian Focus Group	Results: 300 people reached, 9 "Like", 107 "Click".
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1623 "Followers"	01/12/2016	Commission launches Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition	Results: RT of @eSkillsMatch: 1 RT and 1 like
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1623 "Followers"	07/12/2016	Article on e-Skills Match / Newsletter FPM (in Italian language)	Results: 1 RT, 1 like, 437 views and 11 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1623 "Followers"	07/12/2016	Article on e-Skills Match / Newsletter FPM (in English language)	Results: 1 like, 357 views and 2 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1623 "Followers"	07/12/2016	e-Skills Match Project promotional material available on Scribd	Results: RT of @eSkillsMatch: 1 RT and 3 like
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1623 "Followers"	24/02/2017	Photos of e-Skills Match Italian Focus Group	Results: 1 RT, 1 like, 297 views and 3 interactions

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

UAH	Facebook Post	17/02/2017	Inform about the usability workshop performed in the UAH	Facebook post to inform about the workshop carry out in the University of Alcalá to evaluate the usability (and accessibility) of the e-Skills Match Framework
UAH	Facebook Post	21/02/2017	Inform about the article published in a High impact Journal	Facebook post about the publication of an article about the eSkills Match matching model to gain visibility of the results
UAH	Facebook Post	17/01/2017	Inform about the adaptation of e-CF and ESCO competences to a Masters in the University of Alcalá	Facebook post to inform about the adaptation of competences of two Masters programs to map them to e-CF and ESCO performed by the University of Alcalá
UAH	Facebook Post	01/12/2016	Article about the different standards that are coming from European for ICT professionals qualification	Facebook post to provide more visibility to the article about the different standards that are coming from European for ICT professionals qualification
UAH	Facebook Post	13/02/2017	Article which shows how to start connecting different European Models for ICT competences and profiles	Facebook post to provide more visibility to the article where it is shown how to start connecting different European Models for ICT competences and profiles
UAH	Facebook Post	02/12/2016	Event where the different digital qualifications	Facebook post to provide more visibility to the event where the different digital

			standards (eCF, ESCO, etc.) in Europe were presented together with results from projects like ecf Council and eSkills Match	qualifications standards (eCF, ESCO, etc.) in Europe were presented together with results from projects like ecf Council and eSkills Match
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan-page has 1771 "Like".	24/05/2017	Save the date event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT" Politecnico di Milano, Aula Magna – P.zza L. da Vinci 32, Milano (01/06/2017 – 9:30)	Results: 2997 people reached, 45 "Like", 44 "Click", 12 "Sharing".
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan-page has 1771 "Like".	30/05/2017	Promotion of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT"	Results: 1232 people reached, 13 "Like", 15 "Click", 4 "Sharing".
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fans' page has 1771 "Like".	01/06/2017	Promotion of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT" (Photo gallery)	Results: 1331 people reached, 4 "Like", 48 "Click", 1 "Sharing".
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fans' page has 1771 "Like".	01/06/2017	Promotion of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale"	Results: 176 people reached, 7 "Like", 45 "Click".

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

			nell'ICT" (Photo gallery + Summary of the event)	
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan page has 1771 "Like".	13/07/2017	Sharing from the project account: promotion of the web platform and survey	Results: 125 people reached, 5 "Like", 1 "Click".
FPM	Facebook FPM FPM fan page has 1771 "Like".	20/07/2017	Communication of the new project press release and promotion of the web platform and survey	Results: 753 people reached, 4 "Like", 12 "Click", 1 "Sharing".
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	25/05/2017	Save the date event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT" Politecnico di Milano, Aula Magna – P.zza L. da Vinci 32, Milano (01/06/2017 – 9:30)	Results: 1 RT, 3 like, 610 views and 12 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	30/05/2017	Promotion of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT"	Results: 5 RT, 5 like, 632 views and 16 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	01/06/2017	Live 74dfor7474g of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di	Results: 3 RT, 2 like, 1.123 views and 10 interactions

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

			sviluppo professionale nell'ICT"	
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	01/06/2017	Live 75dfor7575g of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT"	Results: 7 RT, 7 like, 1.340 views and 32 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	01/06/2017	Live 75dfor7575g of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT"	Results: 4 RT, 4 like, 1.098 views and 13 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	01/06/2017	Live 75dfor7575g of the event "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell'ICT"	Results: 4 RT, 5 like, 1.053 views and 19 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	13/07/2017	RT from the project account: promotion of the web platform and survey	Results: 4 RT, 5 like, 1.053 views and 19 interactions
FPM	Twitter FPM FPM profile has 1799 "Followers"	20/07/2017	Communication of the new project press release and promotion of the web platform and survey	Results: 3 RT, 4 like, 427 views and 12 interactions

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

FPM	Direct Email Marketing / FPM e-newsletter	24/05/2017	We sent the save the date of our event to a targeted mailing list, counting about 11.500 contacts	Results: 1.587 emails opened and read
FPM	Direct Email Marketing / FPM e-newsletter	29/05/2017	We sent a recall of our event to a targeted mailing list, counting about 1.500 contacts	Results: 262 emails opened and read
FPM	Direct Email Marketing / FPM e-newsletter	30/05/2017	We sent the invitation to the event using the FPM monthly digital newsletter and mailing lists, counting about 30.000 contacts	Results: 2.290 emails opened and read
FPM	Direct Email Marketing / FPM e-newsletter	August-September 2017	We planned to send a recall on press release, web platform and survey using the FPM monthly digital newsletter and mailing lists, counting about 30.000 contacts	
UAH	Facebook Post	26/06/2017	Article written by Professor Luis Fernández Sanz entitled where it is shown different European projects related to ICT professional profiles.	Facebook post about the publication of an article about European projects related to ICT professional profiles.

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

UAH	Facebook Post	09/06/2017	Project's presentation carried out in a event entitled "Marcos europeos de competencias profesionales TIC: Experiencias y proyectos" carried out in the University of Alcalá on June 7 th , 2017.	Facebook post to inform about the Project's presentation carried out in a event entitled "Marcos europeos de competencias profesionales TIC: Experiencias y proyectos"
UAH	Facebook Post	12/06/2017	Workshop focused to professionals, held at the University of Alcalá to present and evaluate the Skills Match project's platform carried out in the University of Alcalá on June 7 th , 2017.	Facebook post to inform about the Workshop performed at the University of Alcalá about the Skills Match project's platform.
UAH	Facebook Post	16/06/2017	Workshop focused to students, held at the University of Alcalá to present and evaluate the eSkills Match project's platform carried out in the University of Alcalá on June 14 th , 2017.	Facebook post to inform about the Workshop carried out by the University of Alcalá to present the eSkills Match project's platform.
UAH	Facebook Post	26/06/2017	Monograph about Professional training and specialized training in cyber	Facebook post to inform about the publication of Monograph related to Professional training and specialized

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

			security where it is presented the project (In Spanish)	training in cyber security where the project is presented.
UAH	Facebook Post	26/06/2017	Presentation of the project carried out in “Future Jobs” event, where it was spoken about digital competences for professionals and users carried out in Coruña on 15/06/2017	Facebook post about the presentation of the project carried out in “Future Jobs” event.
UAH	Facebook Post	06/06/2017	Project’s Presentation in the Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition in AMETIC to the main national stakeholders carried out in Madrid on June 5 th , 2017.	Facebook post about project’s Presentation in the Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition in AMETIC.
ADFOR	May Adfor news Mass mailing > 3000 contacts	10/05/17	Periodic mailing	General mail showing Adfor news, including eSkill Mach activities
ADFOR	June Adfor news Mass mailing > 3000 contacts	28/05/17	Periodic Mailing	General mail showing Adfor news, including eSkill Mach activities

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2U	Send "Holiday Greetings Cards" via e-mail to Stakeholders	15/12/ 2016	To communicate the e-skills match project to wider circle of stakeholders and increase the visibility of the project.	We sent greeting card e-mails to 1828 stakeholders (ICT academics, research community, ESN, Europe Direct, Immigration Boards, Employment offices, refugee organizations, ICT organizations, similar projects, extra-curricular schools etc.) in order to communicate the e-Skills match project to a wider audience.
Gov2u	Press release	19/07/2017	To announce the availability of the e-Skills Match platform and invite end users to test it.	We sent the press release to 3000 stakeholder contacts (ICT academics, research community, ESN, Europe Direct, Immigration Boards, Employment offices, refugee organizations, ICT organizations, similar projects, extra-curricular schools etc.) for promoting the e-Skills Match platform in pan-European level.
Gov2u	e-Newsletter	26/09/2017	Annual newsletter issue to announce the availability of the platform and promote the e-Skills Match videos	We sent the annual newsletter issue to 3000 stakeholders' contacts and the newsletter subscribers.
Gov2u	Press release	28/09/2017	To announce the end of project's lifecycle.	We sent the press release to 3000 stakeholder contacts for announcing the end of the project.
Gov2u	www.kariera.gr	14/07/2017	To inform about e-Skills Match objectives and invite	We communicated through the e-Skills Match LinkedIn account by sending

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

	(the most popular portal in Greece for employers and jobseekers), online communication via LinkedIn		to support the project by disseminating it through the kariera.gr website	inbox message to the profile of kariera.gr on LinkedIn (connection of the e-Skills Match profile on LinkedIn)
Gov2u	Cedefop, online communication via its website	20/07/2017	To inform about e-Skills Match objectives and invite to support the project by disseminating the launch of the project's platform.	We communicated through its website (communication form). No response received.
Gov2u	OAED (Greek employment office), online communication via email and its website	20/07/2017	To inform about e-Skills Match objectives and invite to support the project by using the platform and try to inform unemployed young people in Greece.	We sent the invitation to the organization's email and also at its website (communication form) in order to make sure that this message will be successfully transmitted. No response received.
Gov2u	Ms. Katerina Zourou, Ph.D. (Director, Web2Learn e-learning company), online communication via email	21/06/2017	To inform about the e-Skills Match and raise its visibility to companies and individuals who have professional experience on MOOCs and e-learning in general.	Ms. Zourou had worked in LangOER project (EU funded project) which concerned online learning.
Adfor	Web mail	Adfor news September 2016	Periodic newsletter with ecf mention.	General information about Adfor activities, including eCF related projects

Adfor	Web mail	Adfor news December 2016	Periodic newsletter with ecf mention	General information about Adfor activities, including eCF related projects
Adfor	Web mail	Adfor news February 2017	Periodic newsletter with ecf mention	General information about Adfor activities, including eCF related projects
Adfor	Web mail	Adfor news March 2017	Periodic newsletter with ecf mention	General information about Adfor activities, including eCF related projects

Table 20 : Communication with stakeholders

APPENDIX XI – Participation in third party events

Partner's Name	Name of the event	Date of the event	Location of the event (city, country)	Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)	Outcome of the activity
FPM	Convegno Competenze Digitali in Sanità (Digital competences in healthcare)	26 September 2016	Ministry of Health, Rome, Italy	Presentation of results of a national survey on digital competences in the healthcare sector at national level in Italy	Alignment on state-of-the-art of eCompetences in healthcare sector in Italy
FPM	e-leadership e digital skills in sanità (e-leadership and digital skills in healthcare)	30 September 2016	ASL Torino 3, Collegno, Italy	Discussion of digital competences in the healthcare organizations in Italy with members of ASL Torino 3 (local healthcare authority in Turin area – Italy)	Collection of the point of view of a local healthcare authority in Italy on digital competencies
eGovlab	Lab Connections	17-18 October 2016	Brussels	eGovlab was in Lab Connections where policy labs 82dfor82 the EU exchanged knowledge on current projects they are working on. This was done in the form of networking and workshops within the European Commission's premises in Brussels. Approx. 150 people were there.	Increase awareness of project in an EU level with other policy labs and EC members.

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Adfor	Ecf In Actiom	25 October 2016	Rome, Italy	Event where eCf framework is presented in a workshop with main Italian company	Informative event about the eCf capabilities thru ecf Plua, an AICA tool
UAH	Andaira	30 November 2016	Madrid, Spain	Event where the different digital qualifications standards in Europe were presented	Informative event about the different standards that are coming from Europe for ICT professionals qualification
eGovlab	Samverkansprojekt/ Collaboration: University and the wider Society	22 February 2017	Stockholm	eGovlab presented the project during a 2-day event on Research and implentations of ICT to support Inclusion, Integration and Development. Approx. 40 people attended from research institutes and Samverkansavdelningen. The event supported research activities and education through networking and communication.	Increase awareness of eSkills March project within Swedish academic sphere.
ADFOR	Compliance day	16 May 2017	Milano, c/o Assolombarda	Conference attendees (about 300 people, attending 1 day conference)	e-competence presentation (specif. PM and Compliance)
eGovlab	Creative Entrepreneurship Academy: eGovernance Edition 2017	19 May 2017	Tallinn Estonia	The CEA is both a theoretical and hands-on experience in e-governance. CEA is providing creative techniques for	Dissemination of platform in other EU countries and

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

				<p>innovative practices and solutions.</p> <p>The 2017 edition focused on the making of places by inclusive public e-services and e-products. CEA offers dialogue platform for public sector, business community (IT-businesses, start-ups etc.) and creatives, with the aim to consider the factors stimulating innovation in the e-governance. For businesses and creatives, CEA provides insight to public sectors expectations and requirements in ordering e-products or e-services. CEA offered an opportunity to develop ideas into e-products and e-services by professional coaching throughout the academy.</p>	<p>potential for new collaborations</p>
FPM	eCF COUNCIL Workshop on ICT competences	01 June 2017	Politecnico di Milano, Aula F1.1 P.zza L. Da Vinci 32, Milano (Italy) 13:45 – 15:00	<p>The workshop was addressed to a class of third year students in Computer Science. It introduced the debate on ICT competences and development as the standard deals with (eCF). It presented eSKM project and platform,</p>	<p>It promoted the project within the academic target and explained its relation with the European panorama.</p>

				promoting the testing access and online evaluation survey.	
UAH	AMETIC	05 June 2017	Madrid, Spain	<p>Presentation about activities performed by the Digital Skills and Jobs.</p> <p>20, representatives of companies and organizations participating in the Coalition</p>	Project's Presentation on an event of the Digital Skills and Jobs to promote the results of the project to a group of representatives of companies and organizations
UAH	Future Jobs	15 June 2017	La Coruña, Spain	<p>Day training about the new trends in the labor market, marked by technological progress and the digital society.</p> <p>100, students, teachers and labor orientation agents</p>	Project's Presentation on an event of the Digital Skills and Jobs to promote the results of the project to a group of students, teachers and labor orientation agents

Table 21 : Participation in third party events

APPENDIX XII – Media Coverage

<i>Partner's Name</i>	<i>Type of press item (press release, interview, etc.)</i>	<i>Title of the press item</i>	<i>Media where it was published</i>	<i>URL (if available)</i>
eGovlab	Website link	Meeting: Samverkansprojekt/Collaboration: University and the wider Society	DSV website	http://dsv.su.se/en/about/events/meeting-samverkansprojekt-collaboration-university-and-the-wider-society-1.320254
FPM	Article on FPM newsletter (FPM website, October 2016)	e-skills Match, nuove competenze per i professionisti dell'ICT	www.fondazionepolitecnico.it	http://bit.ly/2fC60fe
FPM	Article on FPM newsletter (printed version, October 2016)	e-skills Match, nuove competenze per i professionisti dell'ICT	Fondazionepolitecnico.it	
UAH	Article	e-Skills Match: A framework for mapping and integrating the main skills, knowledge and competence standards and models for ICT occupations	Computer Standards & Interfaces	http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0920548916301593
UAH	Article	Los estándares que vienen de Europa para la cualificación de los profesionales TIC	Tecnonews	http://www.tecnonews.info/opiniones/los_estandares_que_vienen_de_europa_para_la_cualificacion_de_los_profes

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

UAH	Article	How to start connecting the different European models for ICT competences and profiles	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4943197/4943197-6227802625681690626
UAH	Web	Mention to the direct application for expertise developed with the project on UAH website for Master on Web Software Engineering	UAH's Website	http://bit.ly/MapaECFMasterWeb
UAH	Web	Mention to the direct application for expertise developed with the project on UAH website for Master on IT Project Management	UAH's Website	http://bit.ly/MapaECFMasterProyectos
Adfor	Web	ECF in azione	Adfor website	http://www.adfor.it/news/e-cf-in-azione
Adfor	Web	Adfor partecipa a l progetto ecf	Adfor Website	http://www.adfor.it/newsletter/genaio-2017/adfor-e-skill-match-ecf
FPM	FPM Website – Home page The FPM website has about 7.000 page views per month. From 23/05/2017 to 01/06/2017 Results: 492 views, 365 unique visitors	Promotion of the event “Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell’ICT”	Web	

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

FPM	<p>FPM Website – Page Detail</p> <p>The FPM website has about 7.000 page views per month.</p> <p>23/05/2017 – still active</p> <p>Results: 252 views, 205 unique visitors</p>	Promotion of the event “Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale nell’ICT”	Web	http://www.fondazionepolitecnico.it/eventi/eventi/competenze-digitali-mercato-e-percorsi-di-sviluppo-professionale-nell-ict-progetto-e-skills-match#.WXigsYSLTIU
UAH	Web	Promotion of the e-Skills Match platform	Pledge Viewer website	http://pledgeviewer.eu/pledges/department-of-computer-sciences-university-of-alcala-79.html
FPM	Project Video	Paolo Locatelli, FPM di Milano, explains benefits of e-Skills Match in e-Health sector	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DW7R7zyUodo
FPM	Project Video	Lorenza Leita, FPM, introducing e-CF (EN16234) and ESCO	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H9PWN1ykv50
FPM	Project Video	Lorenza Leita, FPM, explains e-competence self assessment in e-Skills Match	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LNHcjI67mpE
UAH	Project video	e-SkillsMatch for ICT training providers and employers	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I7t7OqUou6Y
SU	Project video	e-Skills Match – The Self-Assessment	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3TlaC8FW4KU

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

SU	Project video	e-Skills Match – The Employer	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CdO_uwHEki8
SU	Project video	e-Skills Match – The ePortfolio	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Es0N9-NJHk4
SU	Project video	e-Skills Match – The Training Section	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=d4uOeYJYdfI
SU	Project video	e-Skills Match – The Training Institution	YouTube Channel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SQIjU9atyVc
FPM	Facebook post	Lorenza Leita, Competence Valorization projects in Fondazione Politecnico di Milano, explains in this video how the E-Skills Match project self assessment may help people empowering their professional profile and marketability.	FPM Facebook page	https://www.facebook.com/Fondazione.Politecnico.di.Milano/posts/1689553654413052
FPM	FPM Website – Project page e-SKM Both in Italian and English language. Direct Links to the official eSKM website and social media. The FPM website has about 7.000 page views per month.	e-SKILLS MATCH	Web	Italian version http://www.fondazionepolitecnico.it/en/component/zoo/item/e-skills-match#.WXiz74SLTIU English version http://www.fondazionepolitecnico.it/en/component/zoo/item/e-skills-match-project#.WXizp4SLTIU

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

	Publication: 03/12/2015. The project web page will last active after the project on the FPM website.			
UAH	Article	Monograph about Professional training and specialized training in cyber security where it is presented the project (In Spanish)	Instituto Español de Estudios Estratégicos. Departamento de Seguridad Nacional	https://portal.uah.es/portal/page/portal/grupos_de_investigacion/94/Proyectos/repositorio/archivos/Capacitacion_profesional_y_formacion_especializada_en_ciberseguridad.pdf
UAH	Article	Article written by Professor Luis Fernández Sanz entitled where it is shown different European projects related to ICT professional profiles. (In Spanish)	AENUI	http://www.aenui.net/ojs/index.php?journal=revision&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=336&path%5B%5D=514
UAH	Press Release	e-Skills Match Prototype Platform Open until the 31 st of August	CEPIS	http://mailchi.mp/692b37ce5f2e/itp-e-news-flash-e-skills-match?e=af1b625220
UAH	Newsletter	e-Skills Match Launches New Prototype Platform	CEPIS	https://www.cepis.org/index.jsp?p=641&n=1035#16
UAH	Book chapter	Analysis of the European ICT Competence Frameworks	Journal of Human Capital and Information Technology Professionals (IJHCITP)	Submitted to the journal for further publication

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

ADFOR	ADFOR website, home page, news, link, periodic update ADFOR website has 20.000 unique visitors per month	June-July link to "Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale ICT" August link to Press release "E' disponibile la piattaforma e-Skills Match"	web	http://www.adfor.it
ADFOR	ADFOR website, detail page – 570 visitors in the reporting period	"e-CF Assessment delle competenze"	web	http://www.adfor.it/risorse-umane/ict-assessment-e-cf-based
ADFOR	ADFOR website, detail page with updates– 455 visitors in the reporting period	"Adfor partecipa al progetto e-Skill Match"	web	http://www.adfor.it/newsletter/genaio-2017/adfor-e-skill-match-ecf
ADFOR	ADFOR website, detail page – 196 visitors	"Competenze digitali, mercato e percorsi di sviluppo professionale ICT" (workshop by FPM promotion)	web	http://www.adfor.it/news/skills-match-evento-1-giugno-2017
ADFOR	ADFOR website, detail page – 34 downloads	Workshop by FPM: program and invitation	web	http://www.adfor.it/site/utility.php?a=download&cb=GITEMS&to=download&s=1061&iditem=2904
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster Y2 (English Version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster-y2-english-version

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet Y2 (English Version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-factsheet-y2-english-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Swedish version	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster-shorter-version-swedish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Swedish version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster-swedish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Swedish version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-factsheet-swedish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster-shorter-version-spanish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster-spanish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-factsheet-spanish-version

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skill Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Greek version	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskill-match-project-poster-shorter-version-greek-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skill Match Project Poster (Greek version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskill-match-project-poster-greek-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Greek version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-factsheet-greek-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Poster (shorter version) - Italian version	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-poster-shorter-version-italian-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Italian version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster-italian-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Italian version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-factsheet-italian-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Poster (shorter version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-poster-shorter-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Poster	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-poster

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-factsheet
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure Y2 (English version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/e-skills-match-project-brochure-y2-english-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Flyer Y2 (English Version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-flyer-y2-english-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Swedish version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-brochure-swedish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-brochure-spanish-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Greek version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-brochure-greek-version
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Italian version)	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-brochure-italian-version

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-brochure
Gov2U	Slideshare Post	e-Skills Match Project Overall Presentation - year 1	e-Skills Match Slideshare account	https://www.slideshare.net/eSkillsMatch/eskills-match-project-overall-presentation-year-1
Gov2u	PlayBuzz post	Map Your journey to a new carrier	PlayBuzz	https://www.playbuzz.com/ateivag10/map-your-journey-to-a-new-career
Gov2u	Facebook post	Explanatory video about the #training section of the E-Skills Match #platform	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155701515996057
Gov2u	Twitter post	Explanatory video about the #training section of the E-Skills Match #platform	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/903217724482048000
Gov2u	Facebook post	Easy steps to manage your #ePortfolio (E-Skills Match)	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155694908616057
Gov2u	Twitter post	Easy steps to manage your #ePortfolio (E-Skills Match)	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/902482236448047105
Gov2u	Facebook post	The #Self_Assessment_Tool of the E-Skills Match #platform	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155694889336057
Gov2u	Twitter post	e-Skills Match - Usability Workshop in Athens	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/840133370667446272

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Facebook post	Learn how the E-Skills Match #self_assessment #tool may help you empower your #professional_profile and #marketability	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155692318181057
Gov2u	Twitter post	The e-Skills Match #videos are now available!!	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/893413515326885892
Gov2u	Facebook post	E-Skills Match featured at Bizmooc website! "Are you ready to take your #career to the next level?"	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155692106911057
Gov2u	Twitter post	E-Skills Match featured at Bizmooc website!	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/902120663229632512
Gov2u	Facebook post	The e-Skills Match #videos are now available!! You can find them at our project's website on section #Media:	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155619180751057
Gov2u	Twitter post	Learn how the E-Skills Match #self_assessment #tool may help you empower your #professional_profile and #marketability	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/902151551426461700
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match for ICT training providers and employers	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155616434841057

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Twitter post	Easy steps to manage your #ePortfolio (E-Skills Match)	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/902482236448047105
Gov2u	Facebook post	Map your Journey to a new career - Test the E-Skills Match platform at: https://platform.eskillsmatch.eu/login	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155597733171057
Gov2u	Twitter post	Explanatory video about the #training section of the E-Skills Match #platform	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/903217724482048000
Gov2u	Facebook post	The E-Skills Match #Press_Release featured on #Joinup!!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155571953486057
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match featured on CEPIS latest newsletter issue!!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155568400221057
Gov2u	Facebook post	Check out the press release that Gov2U team has created as a partner in the EU project, E-Skills Match!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155567782346057
Gov2u	Facebook post	Want to know how your ICT skills measure up to your future career? #Test and #find_out!	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155530485921057
Gov2u	Facebook post	Η ΓΝΩΜΗ ΣΟΥ ΜΕΤΡΑΕΙ: ΑΞΙΟΛΟΓΗΣΕ ΤΗΝ ΠΛΑΤΦΟΡΜΑ E-Skills Match	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155453700126057

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match Usability Workshop by Universidad de Alcala (UAH)	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155174080076057
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match - Usability workshop by ADFOR	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155119464711057
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match - Usability workshop by Fondazione Politecnico di Milano (FPM)	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155119464011057
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match - Usability Workshops in Athens	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10155097647656057
Gov2u	Facebook post	The e-Skills Match project platform is available for users. Find YOUR Top Profile Matches	ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/ICA.IT.ORG/posts/1904509129816652
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match – Press Release	ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/ICA.IT.ORG/posts/1887914648142767
Gov2u	Twitter post	e-Skills Match – Press Release	ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration Twitter account	https://twitter.com/IcaCouncil/status/888011068471209984

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Twitter post	The e-Skills Match project platform is available for users. Find YOUR Top Profile Matches	ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration Twitter account	https://twitter.com/IcaCouncil/status/902430762120699904
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match – The training section (YouTube video)	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1699812523386874&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	Learn how the E-Skills Match #self_assessment #tool may help you empower your #professional_profile and #marketability	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1696840320350761&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	E-Skills Match featured at Bizmooc website! "Are you ready to take your #career to the next level?"	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1696754700359323&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	The e-Skills Match #videos are now available!! You can find them at our project's website on section #Media:	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1671071962927597&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match for ICT training providers and employers	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1670135579687902&id=215302701837871

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Facebook post	Map your Journey to a new career - Test the E-Skills Match platform at:	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1663288017039325&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	E-Skills Match #Platform #Available For #Testing – #Press_release – #Second_Year	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1653345151366945&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	Η ΓΝΩΜΗ ΣΟΥ ΜΕΤΡΑΕΙ: ΑΞΙΟΛΟΓΗΣΕ ΤΗΝ ΠΛΑΤΦΟΡΜΑ E-Skills Match	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1616084838426310&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	e-Skills Match Overall presentation also available on Slideshare!! Spread the word out and let's tackle together youth unemployment in Europe!	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1320438991324231&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Facebook post	Begin your journey to a new career!!!!	MyUniversity Project Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=1309121532455977&id=215302701837871
Gov2u	Website article	E-SKILLS MATCH PLATFORM AVAILABLE FOR TESTING – PRESS RELEASE – Y2	Gov2u website	http://gov2u.org/index.php/learn/news/314-e-skills-match-platform-available-for-testing-press-release-y2
Gov2u	Website article	e-Skills Match honored with EU's Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition Membership!	Gov2u website	http://gov2u.org/index.php/learn/news/315-eskills-match-honored-with-eu-s-digital-skills-and-jobs-coalition-membership

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Issuu post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet Y2 (English version)	e-Skills Match Issuu.com account	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/factsheety2_webv
Gov2u	Issuu post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure Y2 (English version)	e-Skills Match Issuu.com account	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/e-skills_match_project_brochure_y2
Gov2u	Issuu post	e-Skills Match Project Flyer Y2 (English version)	e-Skills Match Issuu.com account	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/flyer-eskills_for-web
Gov2u	Issuu post	e-Skills Match Project Poster Y2 (English version)	e-Skills Match Issuu.com account	https://issuu.com/e-skillsmatch/docs/poster_for-web
Gov2u	Pinterest post	e-Skills Match - The ePortfolio - YouTube	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557566/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	e-Skills Match - The Training Institution - YouTube	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557532/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	e-Skills Match - The Training Section - YouTube	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557527/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	e-Skills Match - The Self-Assessment - YouTube	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557517/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	Map your journey to a new career	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884557526/

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Pinterest post	e-Skills Match for ICT training providers and employers	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576082/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	Paolo Locatelli, FPM di Milano, explains benefits of e-Skills Match in e-Health sector	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576087/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	Lorenza Leita, FPM, introducing e-CF (EN16234) and ESCO	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576111/
Gov2u	Pinterest post	Lorenza Leita, FPM, explains e-competence self-assessment in e-Skills Match	e-Skills Match Pinterest account	https://gr.pinterest.com/pin/596304806884576118/
Gov2u	Instagram post	Photo	e-Skills Match Instagram account	https://www.instagram.com/p/BSfI8tBWII/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject
Gov2u	Instagram post	Photo	e-Skills Match Instagram account	https://www.instagram.com/p/BRdBJ0Biap/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject
Gov2u	Instagram post	Photo	e-Skills Match Instagram account	https://www.instagram.com/p/BQ2YZRXBNhD/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject
Gov2u	Instagram post	Photo	e-Skills Match Instagram account	https://www.instagram.com/p/BQz1eolBchD/?taken-by=eskillsmatchproject

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327168946/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Italian version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327192602/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-Italian-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Italian version	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327192609/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-shorter-version-Italian-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Greek version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327193216/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-Greek-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Italian version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327192610/e-Skills-Match-Project-Brochure-Italian-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Greek version	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327193218/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-shorter-version-Greek-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Greek version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327193342/e-Skills-Match-Project-Brochure-Greek-version

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Greek version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327193456/e-Skills-Match-Project-Factsheet-Greek-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Swedish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327193894/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-Swedish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Swedish version	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327193909/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-shorter-version-Swedish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Swedish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194000/e-Skills-Match-Project-Brochure-Swedish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Swedish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194118/e-Skills-Match-Project-Factsheet-Swedish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Overall Presentation	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327167896/e-Skills-Match-Project-Overall-Presentation
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194396/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-Spanish-version

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194407/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-shorter-version-Spanish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194447/e-Skills-Match-Project-Brochure-Spanish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194474/e-Skills-Match-Project-Factsheet-Spanish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Flyer (English version) - Year 2	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/341293077/e-Skills-Match-Project-Flyer-English-version-Year-2
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (shorter version) - Spanish version	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194407/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-shorter-version-Spanish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Brochure (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194447/e-Skills-Match-Project-Brochure-Spanish-version
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (English version) - Year 2	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/341293107/e-Skills-Match-Project-Factsheet-English-version-Year-2

D6.1c Final report of communication and dissemination activities

Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Poster (English version) - Year 2	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/341293200/e-Skills-Match-Project-Poster-English-version-Year-2
Gov2u	Scribd post	e-Skills Match Project Factsheet (Spanish version)	e-Skills Match Scribd account	https://www.scribd.com/document/327194474/e-Skills-Match-Project-Factsheet-Spanish-version
Gov2u	LinkedIn post	e-Skills Match Platform Available For Testing – Press release	LinkedIn group - Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4943197/4943197-6296627711553212419
Gov2u	LinkedIn post	e-Skills Match Project: Easy steps to manage your ePortfolio	LinkedIn group - Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4943197/4943197-6308281282174550020
Gov2u	LinkedIn post	Potential benefits of e-Skills Match in e-Health sector	LinkedIn group - Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4943197/4943197-6299208188365537283
Gov2u	News article	e-Skills Match Platform Available For Testing – Press release – Y2	Joinup	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/e-skills-match-platform-available-testing-%E2%80%93-press-release-%E2%80%93-y2
Gov2u	News article	Are you ready to take your career to the next level?	BizMOOC project's website	http://bizmooc.eu/are-you-ready-to-take-your-career-to-the-next-level/?platform=hootsuite

Table 22 : Media coverage